

Natural Ventilation Technique: A Bibliometric Analysis of Research Trends

Noor Roziana Binti Abdul Rahim^{1,*}, Péter Szabó¹, Zsolt Kovács¹

¹Jozsef Cziraki Doctoral School of Wood Sciences and Technologies, University of Sopron, Hungary

*Author to whom correspondence should be addressed:
E-mail: abdul.rahim.noorroziana@phd.uni-sopron.hu

(Received April 26, 2024; Revised February 19, 2025; Accepted April 01, 2025)

Abstract: Contemporary design often neglects natural ventilation, worsening energy consumption. Combining eco-friendly design with architectural principles can mitigate this issue. The VOS viewer program, a tool for visualizing the bibliometric analysis of research trends on natural ventilation techniques, has been used, focusing on their role in improving energy efficiency and reducing cooling demands. The analysis examines 3,651 papers that discuss natural ventilation, focusing on its role in improving energy efficiency and reducing cooling demands in residential buildings. The study identifies key patterns and emerging passive techniques like windcatcher, woodcarving, Mashrabiya, Kumiko, and latticework, as well as areas for future research. The study also identifies funding gaps in the research and suggests targeted strategies, mainly passive ventilation methods.

Keywords: energy efficiency, natural ventilation, passive technique, traditional architecture

1. Introduction

The Earth's surface receives substantial solar radiation, creating a persistent demand for cooling in buildings and amplifying the need for sustainable architectural solutions¹. Concurrently, Human activities, such as burning forests, clearing agricultural lands, and excessive use of fossil fuels² have led to increased levels of greenhouse gases in the troposphere³ contributing to climate change and the depletion of the ozone layer^{4,5}. These environmental challenges are compounded by the energy demands of buildings, which are responsible for a significant portion of global energy consumption⁶.

Buildings significantly contribute to energy consumption, with studies indicating that 35% to 49% of energy in residential and industrial sectors is dedicated to maintaining comfortable indoor conditions⁷. Sustainable architecture, seeking to optimise energy efficiency and enhance occupant well-being, has become pivotal in the face of environmental challenges posed by conventional practices^{8,9}. Especially in the construction industry, the imperative for energy-efficient buildings is paramount¹⁰. Moreover, investigating renewable energy sources presents promising options for replacing fossil fuels in both power generation and industrial sectors^{11,12}. Some renewable energy prospects encompass solar cells¹³, wind¹⁴, geothermal^{15,16}, and bioenergy^{17,18}. Wind energy stands out among renewable energy sources due to its

consistently increasing potential for development and expansion with each passing year¹⁹.

The popularity of energy efficiency is rising alongside advancements in global environmental protection efforts²⁰. Incorporating energy efficiency measures by the building industry can notably decrease carbon emissions, with the utilisation of energy-efficient building materials being a prominent strategy²¹. Buildings are now being designed with a strong emphasis on providing occupants maximum comfort and convenience while minimising energy usage. This focus on energy management has become crucial in the present era^{22,23,24}. Natural ventilation (NV) plays a vital role in sustainable building design, offering a range of benefits, including reducing building energy consumption, improving thermal comfort, and promoting a healthy indoor environment²⁵. Numerous studies indicate that NV can potentially decrease building cooling loads²⁶ and effectively reduce classroom energy demands while enhancing indoor air quality²⁷. Other than that, using natural materials in traditional houses has been demonstrated to reduce energy consumption and carbon footprint while ensuring thermal comfort²⁸. Integrating traditional design with modern solutions represents a promising approach to sustainable architectural design²⁹.

In this context, the role of NV emerges as a critical consideration, offering a potential alternative to energy-intensive HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) systems. The HVAC system is responsible

for maintaining indoor air quality and regulating the temperature of buildings by providing both cooling and heating functions³⁰. However, studies suggest the potential for NV to significantly reduce energy consumption, with reported reductions of 10-45% in HVAC costs when coupled with radiant systems³¹⁾³².

Traditional dwellings, shaped by local conditions and economic constraints, are exemplars of passive building strategies³³. These structures, designed using native materials and passive methods, can provide valuable insights into sustainable building practices³⁴⁾³⁵⁾³⁶, demonstrating the potential to achieve thermal comfort and energy efficiency with minimal energy consumption and material waste³⁷. Architectural researchers are increasingly focusing on traditional methods and materials to improve the sustainability and energy efficiency of buildings³⁸.

Incorporating traditional passive design principles into contemporary building planning can significantly enhance indoor comfort and energy efficiency³⁹⁾⁴⁰⁾⁴¹. By adapting strategies from vernacular architecture and passive design techniques, such as optimising shading systems and utilising natural ventilation⁴², buildings can achieve improved thermal performance and sustainability, particularly in hot climates. These strategies, integral to vernacular architecture, offer sustainable solutions by leveraging local materials and climatic conditions and are particularly effective in regions with extreme temperatures. Examples of traditional passive design include using courtyards, natural ventilation, and thermal mass to enhance indoor comfort without relying on modern energy-intensive systems. The architecture of South Indian temples incorporates passive design features such as high ceilings and open courtyards, which enhance natural ventilation and thermal comfort⁴³. Courtyards serve as buffer zones that regulate temperature by facilitating air circulation and providing shaded areas, crucial in hot climates like the Middle East and the Mediterranean³³⁾⁴⁴. Traditional buildings are also designed to promote cross ventilation, which is essential for cooling in hot and humid climates. This is achieved through the strategic placement of windows and openings⁴⁵. Some traditional designs incorporate ventilation panels or wind towers to enhance airflow and improve indoor air quality⁴⁶.

Furthermore, traditional construction methods can help maintain and renovate historical buildings, produce sustainable, resilient structures, and boost the future of our built environment⁴⁷. although traditional methods may not consistently achieve adaptive thermal comfort with intermittent active heating sources⁴⁸, passive design strategies can significantly reduce energy consumption and improve indoor thermal comfort. These strategies often include compact house plans, thick walls, and small window openings to retain indoor heat and prevent excessive heat loss and gain⁴⁹.

As the global demand for air conditioning (AC) surges due to climate change, NV can help mitigate the substantial increases in energy demand and CO₂ emissions⁵⁰ predicted by the International Energy Agency (IEA) staggering increase, with 1.8 to 4.1 billion people requiring AC by 2050^{51,52}. The increase in AC use is driven by rising incomes and temperatures, with robust growth expected in middle-income countries⁵³. Addressing the challenge involves rethinking the design of efficient buildings and evaluating the efficacy of air conditioning systems, particularly in tropical climates⁵⁴. Energy-efficient methods for supplying fresh outdoor air are crucial, considering the energy consumption associated with ventilation⁵⁵. Adequate ventilation is essential not only for energy efficiency but also for maintaining occupant health and productivity⁵⁶.

NV is characterised depending on the external conditions⁵⁷, driven by pressure gradient due to wind, temperature difference, and stack effect⁵⁸. The classification of NV is cross ventilation, unilateral ventilation, and stack ventilation, as shown in Figure 1. Cross-ventilation utilises air movement through openings on opposite sides of the building, creating a pressure difference that drives airflow⁵⁹. Unilateral ventilation involves air from one side, influenced by wind angles⁶⁰⁾⁶¹, while stack ventilation relies on buoyancy forces driven by temperature differences to create upward airflow⁶². The stack effect, caused by temperature differences between the inside and outside of a building, can also drive air movement⁶³⁾⁶⁴. The interaction between these external conditions and the airflow in NV has been studied in various experimental and theoretical investigations⁶⁵⁾⁶⁶.

Fig. 1: Natural ventilation classification

To inform sustainable design practices, it is imperative to delve into past, present, and future trends in natural ventilation. Various software options are available for

conducting bibliometric analysis, allowing for examining scientific parameters such as authors, institutions, citations, and collaborations⁶⁷). Drawing from databases like Google Scholar, Scopus, and the Web of Science, bibliometric analysis can offer insights into research patterns, highlight gaps, and guide future investigations⁶⁸). Widely utilised to evaluate quantitative and qualitative research performance indicators in various scientific domains, bibliometric analysis complements expert opinions and provides objective research performance⁶⁹⁷⁰). This study employs bibliometric tools to uncover trends in NV research, spotlight key contributors, and guide future investigations. By bridging traditional and modern practices, this research aims to contribute to the development of sustainable and culturally resonant architectural solutions.

2. Review and the justification for the current review articles

This study uses bibliometric analysis to synthesise and critically evaluate existing knowledge on NV in traditional housing, particularly in the context of cultural and architectural practices. The following sections furnish an exhaustive overview of the rationale and justification behind this review:

2.1. Review of Past and Present Trends

The foundation of this review lies in recognising the evolving discourse surrounding NV in the context of traditional housing. By delving into historical and contemporary literature, the aim is to trace the trajectory of research developments, identifying key milestones and shifts in scholarly focus⁷¹). The evolution of ventilation in traditional dwellings has been shaped by various factors, from the introduction of innovative low-pressure systems in the 19th century⁷²) to the development of stack ventilation strategies⁷³). Various historical cases highlight the significance of architectural details like chimneys in shaping buildings and reflecting societal status⁷⁴). Traditional dwellings, such as those in northeast Hunan province and Macau Mandarin's House, showcase natural ventilation techniques for sustainable living and environmental protection⁷⁵⁷⁶). Ventilative cooling practices, evident in structures like the House of Lords, illustrate how historical buildings achieved thermal comfort through air movement and night-purge ventilation⁷⁷). These practices reflect the interplay between design considerations and user experiences in maintaining indoor quality without reliance on modern mechanical systems. While traditional methods were developed in response to local climates and available materials, modern buildings often need help adapting these techniques due to technological advancement, regulatory standards, and shifts in lifestyle. By examining these historical practices, contemporary architectural design can benefit from the

wisdom and sustainability inherent in traditional ventilation approaches.

2.2. Addressing Critical Themes

This review strategically addresses critical themes related to NV and traditional architecture. It encompasses a comprehensive search strategy, transitioning from broad inquiries into NV and housing-focused investigations into elements like “woodcarving,” “mashrabiya,” “latticework,” and “Kumiko.” Traditional houses, such as those in tropical and Mediterranean regions, leverage vernacular architecture with features like high ceilings, specific window placements, and airflow-enhancing elements⁷⁸⁷⁹). These designs prioritise natural ventilation by incorporating techniques like wind catchers and wide openings with louvres, showcasing the significance of proper airflow management⁸⁰). The design of Mashrabiya or woodcarving elements not only facilitates airflow but also reflects cultural identity, heritage, and local craftsmanship, which makes it relevant to the discussion of sustainable design. Incorporating traditional knowledge into modern architecture can potentially optimise NV in contemporary designs⁸¹). Exploring these features enables a nuanced understanding of their significance in shaping historical and contemporary architectural practices.

2.3. Methodological Rigor

To ensure a robust selection of literature, Scopus was chosen as the primary database due to its comprehensive coverage of scientific resources across multiple disciplines⁸²⁸³). Scopus has demonstrated high recall (95%) and precision (5.1%) in citation searches, outperforming Google Scholar in systematic reviews⁸⁴), and is known for its comprehensive coverage of scientific literature, including scholarly journals, conference papers, and diverse research materials across various disciplines⁸⁵). The search was confined to peer-reviewed scientific journals to maintain academic rigour, focusing on high-quality, credible studies. As illustrated in Figure 2, the systematic approach is designed to progressively refine the focus, moving from a broad overview to targeted investigations. This methodical process enhances the credibility of the review’s findings and conclusions, ensuring that the analysis aligns with the highest standards of academic integrity.

2.4. Visualisation for Deeper Insights

Incorporating VOS Viewer software for visualisation adds a dynamic dimension to the review⁸⁶⁸⁷⁸⁸). This software enables researchers to explore bibliometric networks and visualise relationships between keywords, authors, and other research elements. It allows for identifying trends and patterns in publication growth over time, adding depth to the analysis⁸⁹⁹⁰). Through its advanced algorithms, VOSviewer detects clusters or communities within

networks, offering insights into the structural dynamics of research fields. This functionality closely resembles the modularity optimisation approach used in Gephi for community detection, making it instrumental in revealing the internal structure of bibliometric networks⁹¹.

Additionally, the dual-format compatibility with *.ris and *.csv files enhances the versatility of data interpretation, enabling a comprehensive exploration of scholarly landscapes related to natural ventilation in traditional housing. The visualisation capabilities of VOSviewer not only complement textual analysis but offer unique insights into the interconnections between various research parameters⁹⁰.

3. Materials and Method

3.1. Literature selection

Scopus was selected due to its broad coverage of peer-reviewed journals, which ensures access to high-quality and authoritative studies across multiple disciplines. Scopus articles were retrieved on November 28, 2024; only English articles were selected. The data reviewed spanned from 1964 to 2024, and all Scopus papers were published in peer-reviewed scientific journals. Scopus is widely recognised as a leading database for scientific literature, providing comprehensive metadata and a robust repository of research publications^{92/93}. It gathers data from this repository to create a social graph of scientific authors based on citations among their articles^{94/95}. Figure 2 illustrates a refined keyword string approach to identify relevant literature on residential natural ventilation. Titles, keywords, and abstracts were meticulously filtered and assessed to ensure alignment with the research objectives. A more refined focus on a specific period could reveal trends in adopting certain ventilation techniques or the increasing integration of traditional and modern approaches. The filtering process systematically narrowed the search results based on key criteria such as article relevance to NV in vernacular housing and specific architectural features.

The general search employed the Scopus profile TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (house), resulting in 3651 documents. This broad dataset was subsequently narrowed by introducing the keyword "vernacular," refining the search to TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (vernacular AND house), yielding 391 documents. To explore a broader range of "traditional," "folk," and "indigenous" were incorporated, producing the profile TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (traditional OR folk OR indigenous) AND (vernacular AND house). This approach identified 277 documents specifically focusing on traditional housing practices. The inclusion of terms like "vernacular," "traditional", and "folk" was based on their relevance in capturing research on cultural and regional variations in

NV practices.

To delve deeper into architectural features that enhance NV, a targeted search string was developed: TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (traditional OR folk OR Indigenous) AND (vernacular AND house) AND (windcatcher OR woodcarving OR latticework OR mashrabiya OR Kumiko). This search focused on the role of intricate designs of architectural features such as windcatcher, woodcarving, latticework, mashrabiya, and Kumiko in enhancing natural airflow through ventilation panels, ultimately identifying 53 highly relevant documents.

Fig. 2: Search profile on Scopus database

3.2. Science mapping using VOS viewer software

The selected literature was obtained from Scopus and saved in both *.ris and *.csv file formats. The *.ris format VOSviewer software generates detailed bibliometric maps, illustrating connections between research topics and identifying clusters of related studies. In contrast, the *.csv format is employed for publishing growth analysis in Microsoft Excel 365. VOSviewer is a tool used for visualising and analysing bibliometric networks, helping to uncover relationships between scientific articles, authors, and research topics, offering a comprehensive understanding of the structural and dynamic characteristics of the scientific domain⁹⁶. It aids in clustering related publications, identifying keywords for searching, collaboration partners, seminal papers, and knowledge gaps^{97/98}.

In addition to these capabilities, VOSviewer has been effectively applied in diverse fields, such as mapping articles in physics education and identifying trends in scientific literacy research⁹⁹. The objective of analysing publication growth over time is to ascertain whether there is an upward or downward trend in research output. The rise in scholarly publications also reflects academics' inclinations towards subject matters. Furthermore, the *.csv format can retrieve data on the most influential publications, as indicated by many citations from other scientific papers. In this review, VOSviewer was employed to map the key themes surrounding NV and traditional architectural features like windcatchers or

woodcarvings in modern contexts.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. General Search

From 1964 to 2024, 3,651 research papers were published on the subject matter encompassing the general search keywords TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (house). These keywords were selected to capture scholarly articles related to the optimisation of NV in residential buildings. It represents core themes in improving energy efficiency, air quality, and comfort in building design. The graph displayed a static state between 1964 and 1974 due to the absence of any publications in the Scopus database during this period. Starting in 2004, the number of scholarly articles on these keywords experienced substantial and rapid growth until 2014, when a significant increase was observed (Figure 3). Based on an analysis of the number of publications each year, research trends can be divided into three clear stages of development¹⁰⁰: early, rapid, and deep¹⁰¹. The introduction of the basic principles of NV marked the early stage (1962-2004).

In contrast, the rapid stage (2004 to 2014) coincided with the rise of simulation tools like CFD and increasing interest in energy-efficient building design. The deep stage (2016-2022) reflects a more integrated approach, with advanced simulation techniques and a focus on indoor air quality (IAQ) becoming central to the field. According to Figure 3, the first academic paper on natural ventilation in a residential complex was added to the Scopus database in 1964. The peak years for publication were 2021 and 2022, each with 101 publications. The spike in publications during 2021 and 2022 could be attributed to increased attention on indoor air quality and building ventilation, mainly due to the ongoing global pandemic, which heightened awareness of the importance of airflow and IAQ in residential and public spaces.

Fig. 3: Document by year for general search

Figure 4 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the publication types within the dataset. Most articles constitute 66.6% (2,580) of the total, followed by conference papers at 24.8% (962), highlighting a substantial presence in conference proceedings. Book chapters contribute 2.5% (95), while conference reviews and reviews account for 0.9% (34) and 4.4% (172), respectively. Books represent a smaller portion of 0.4% (16), and the other types make up 0.1% (1-3). Journal articles comprise most publications and typically provide in-depth analysis and case studies, while conference papers present emerging trends and preliminary results. This suggests that much of the research is still evolving, particularly in CFD and IAQ.

Fig. 4: Document by type for general search

Fig. 5: Document by country or territory for general search

Figure 5 shows the publication output for the top 10 countries from 1964 to 2024. China leads with 647 publications, followed by the United States (405) and the United Kingdom (374). Other notable contributors include Japan, Malaysia, India, Italy, Brazil, South Korea, and France. China's dominance in publication numbers may reflect its rapid urbanisation and emphasis on sustainable

building practices. At the same time, countries like the United States and the United Kingdom continue to lead in innovative research on energy efficiency and IAQ.

The ten most-cited papers in Table 1 highlight critical advancements in natural ventilation and building performance. Studies reveal that thermal history and perceived control significantly influence comfort, making these insights essential for tailoring design strategies to diverse climates. Thermal comfort is subjective, with metabolism and acclimatisation influencing how comfort is perceived in different environments¹⁰². These studies underscore the importance of understanding factors like thermal history and perceived control in achieving optimal comfort. This knowledge is critical for enhancing building design strategies to suit different climates better. Since thermal comfort is inherently subjective, individual factors such as metabolism and acclimatisation play significant roles in shaping diverse perceptions of comfort¹⁰³.

Applications extend to healthcare settings, where CFD is crucial for analysing airflow to control airborne contamination, a vital consideration during pandemics like COVID-19. Additionally, CFD aids in understanding pollutant transport, offering actionable insights for enhancing IAQ¹⁰⁴¹⁰⁵.

The integration of life cycle assessment (LCA) with eco-materials is also a focal point, highlighting the potential of locally sourced materials to minimise the environmental impact of building construction. Eco-materials improve IAQ and reduce health risks associated with volatile organic compounds (VOCs), contributing to healthier living environments. The theme of IAQ also examines the persistence of semi-volatile organic compounds (SVOCs) in indoor environments. Studies reveal that a significant portion of SVOCs adsorb onto surfaces, posing health risks that demand attention to improve indoor environmental quality¹⁰⁶¹⁰⁷¹⁰⁸. This research draws attention to the health implications of these pollutants, which is critical for improving indoor environmental quality and occupant well-being. Exposure to SVOCs is linked to various health issues, including irritation and potential carcinogenic effects¹⁰⁹.

Building Information Modelling (BIM), particularly its integration with green building practices to enhance energy efficiency and sustainability. BIM facilitates precise modelling and analysis of energy consumption, leading to substantial improvements in building performance. For instance, a BIM-integrated framework demonstrated a 13.43% reduction in energy consumption

and CO₂ emissions, showcasing its potential in driving sustainability initiatives¹¹⁰. This integration aligns BIM tools with energy-efficient and sustainable design practices, optimising building performance during design and operational phases. By incorporating energy modelling and lifecycle assessment, BIM contributes to better resource management, operational efficiency, and superior sustainability outcomes¹¹¹. Research on sustainable green construction further highlights the importance of ventilation optimisation within building design. For example, a framework utilising GRIHA parameters and BIM tools has been developed to enhance energy management and indoor air quality, underlining the synergistic potential of these technologies in sustainable design¹¹².

In the context of airflow simulation, studies comparing large eddy simulation (LES) and Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) models illustrate critical trade-offs between simulation accuracy and computational cost. LES captures transient flow features and turbulence structures with high precision, making it particularly effective for complex geometries such as U-ducts and cross-ventilated buildings. This capability allows LES to predict airflow and heat transfer phenomena more reliably. Conversely, while computationally less demanding, RANS models often need help with unsteady flow conditions, resulting in inaccuracies in capturing flow separation and internal airflow patterns¹¹³¹¹⁴. While LES provides more detailed and accurate results, especially in complex geometries, RANS models are often sufficient for simpler designs or when computational resources are limited. In the context of NV, LES might be preferred for simulations involving intricate airflow patterns, such as through cross-ventilated buildings. Understanding these trade-offs is essential for selecting the most efficient and accurate methods for simulating building airflow and optimising ventilation strategies. Overall, the papers summarised in Table 1 highlight the increasing reliance on advanced simulation tools such as CFD, BIM, and LCA to address key challenges in building performance. The rising focus on thermal comfort and IAQ reflect growing concerns about occupant health and well-being in residential spaces. At the same time, the use of CFD simulations and BIM indicates the field's shift towards more data-driven and technologically advanced methods for optimising building performance.

Table 1: Top 10 most cited articles on the general search

Title	Journal	Cited	Ref.	Main Findings/ Contributions	Thematic categories
Thermal adaptation in the built environment: A literature review	Energy and Buildings	1194	¹¹⁵	Highlights the role of behavioural adjustment and expectation in thermal comfort. Finds that air-conditioned vs naturally ventilated buildings differ in comfort	Natural ventilation

Cite: N. Abdul Rahim, P. Szabó, Z. Kovács, "Natural Ventilation Technique: A Bibliometric Analysis of Research Trends". Evergreen, 12 (02) 661-688 (2025). <https://doi.org/10.5109/7363467>.

				responses due to thermal history and perceived control,	
Modelling air quality in street canyons: A review	Atmospheric Environment	962	¹¹⁶⁾	reviews microscale dispersion models for assessing urban air quality and pollution control. Discusses monitoring techniques and mathematical models for pollutant dispersion in street canyons.	Natural ventilation
Life cycle assessment of building materials: Comparative analysis of energy and environmental impacts and evaluation of the eco-efficiency improvement potential	Building and Environment	945	¹¹⁷⁾	LCA study comparing eco-materials with common building materials. promotes eco-innovation and local waste use to reduce environmental impact in building production.	Natural ventilation
Ventilation performance prediction for buildings: A method overview and recent applications	Building and Environment	786	¹¹⁸⁾	review CFD and other ventilation models for building performance. Highlights the increasing use of CFD for studying indoor air quality and natural ventilation.	Natural ventilation
Semivolatile organic compounds in indoor environments	Atmospheric Environment	710	¹¹⁹⁾	examines indoor SVOCs and their long persistence in the air. Model's airborne concentrations and exposure pathways to svocs through air to skin transfer.	Natural ventilation
50 years of Computational Wind Engineering: Past, present and future	Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics	634	¹²⁰⁾	reviews the development of CFD in wind engineering for ventilation and wind conditions. Emphasizes the role of CFD and wind tunnel testing in improving simulation accuracy.	Natural ventilation
CFD simulation of cross-ventilation for a generic isolated building: Impact of computational parameters	Building and Environment	465	¹²¹⁾	conduct CFD sensitivity analysis on key parameters for cross-ventilation in buildings. Validates simulations with wind tunnel experiments to improve ventilation assessments.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher
Building Information Modeling (BIM) for green buildings: A critical review and future directions	Automation in Construction	406	¹²²⁾	provides framework for integrating BIM with green building practices. Proposes the "green BIM triangle" to connect BIM attributes with green building attributes.	Natural ventilation
LES over RANS in building simulation for outdoor and indoor applications: A foregone conclusion?	Building Simulation	386	¹²³⁾	compare LES and RANS models in building simulations. Discusses trade-offs between accuracy and computational cost for various building applications.	Natural ventilation
Towards sustainability, energy-efficient and healthy ventilation strategies in buildings: A review	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews	352	¹²⁴⁾	Develop and integrate natural and hybrid ventilation systems with control strategies to optimize energy efficiency and maintain indoor air quality (IAQ). Analyse the influence of occupants' behaviour on energy consumption and indoor climate to improve building performance and occupant health.	Natural ventilation

4.2. Assessment of research clusters: General search

The csv file was uploaded from the Scopus database and inserted into the Vos viewer. For the keywords “natural,” “ventilation and “house,” a minimum threshold for keyword occurrences was set to 5. This means that only those keywords that appeared at least 5 times across the dataset were considered for further analysis. Out of a total of 18100 identified keywords from 3651 documents found on Scopus, only 1000 keywords met this threshold and were retained for visualisation and network analysis. This filtering process helped to focus the research on the most frequently occurring terms, ensuring a more meaningful representation of the key themes within the dataset.

As illustrated in Figure 6, cluster 1 (the largest with 343 items), shown in red, represents a broad and interconnected research theme. It prominently features keywords such as ventilation, thermal comfort, and housing, highlighting the focus on airflow management, sustainable building practices, and occupant well-being in a residential context. Among these, ventilation is the most dominant keyword, with 997 links, a total link strength of 27000, and 2310 occurrences. This signifies its central role in the research network. It connects extensively with other terms, underscoring the widespread academic and practical interest in optimising ventilation systems to improve air quality and energy efficiency. The second prominent keyword, thermal comfort, appears 567 times, with 688 links and a total link strength of 5,980, reflecting the focus on understanding the enhancement of human comfort through natural ventilation strategies, particularly in response to varying climatic conditions. This is particularly significant in addressing varying climatic conditions. In hot and arid climates, for example, natural ventilation has been shown to reduce indoor temperatures by up to 5.3°C, substantially decreasing discomfort hours by 58% during the hottest days. Such improvements are particularly impactful in low-income housing, where passive design solutions can alleviate energy poverty while enhancing thermal comfort¹³⁵). By leveraging natural ventilation, these strategies improve living conditions and provide sustainable and cost-effective solutions for vulnerable populations. Housing ranks third with 428 occurrences, 847 links, and a total link strength of 5,725. This underscores the focus on applying natural ventilation principles within residential settings to improve living conditions sustainably. Adequate home ventilation enhances thermal comfort and dilutes indoor pollutants, improving air quality. For instance, studies have shown that natural ventilation can significantly reduce fine particle concentrations, an essential benefit in humid environments where air quality can directly impact health¹³⁶).

Cluster 2, represented in green, is a significant thematic

area within the dataset, comprising 309 items. The top three keywords in this cluster are air conditioning, indoor pollution, and air quality. This reflects a strong focus on indoor environmental quality and its management through mechanical and natural means.¹³⁷The most prominent keyword in cluster 2 is air conditioning, with 532 occurrences, 916 links, and a total link strength of 7841. This keyword underscores the importance of mechanical ventilation systems in maintaining thermal comfort and controlling indoor climates, particularly in regions with extreme weather conditions. Energy efficiency and the environmental impact of cooling technologies are often discussed, highlighting their critical role in modern building design and operation. The second key term, indoor air pollution, has 498 occurrences, 876 links, and a total link strength of 7942, making it one of the most significant keywords in the entire dataset. This term connects in discussions on the sources and effects of indoor pollutants, such as particular matter and volatile organic compounds, and strategies for their mitigation. Its strong presence in cluster 2 illustrates the intersection of ventilation strategies, including air conditioning and natural ventilation, with public health and environmental sustainability. The third keyword, air quality, appeared 478 times, with 872 links and a total link strength of 6918. This term ties directly to mechanical and natural ventilation, focusing on maintaining healthy indoor environments by controlling pollutants and ensuring adequate airflow. It often overlaps with discussions on regulatory standards, occupants' health, and advanced monitoring technologies. The relevance of these themes was further underscored during the COVID-19 pandemic, where guidelines emphasised frequent mechanical or natural ventilation as a critical measure to maintain acceptable indoor air quality (IAQ). The research highlighted the importance of ventilation frequency over the duration, showcasing its efficacy in adequate air quality management¹³⁷). Cluster 2 reflects a comprehensive focus on the interplay between ventilation technologies, indoor air quality, and public health, emphasising the need for integrated approaches to ensure sustainable and safe indoor environments.

Cluster 3, represented in blue, comprises 235 items and focuses on topics related to airflow dynamics, simulation techniques, and natural ventilation strategies. The top keywords in this cluster- natural ventilation, computational fluid dynamics (CFD), and air- emphasise integrating traditional passive strategies with advanced technological tools to analyse and optimise building airflow. The most significant keyword, natural ventilation, is a central theme in cluster 3, with 1637 occurrences, 952 links, and a total link strength of 17374. It reflects extensive research on passive cooling and ventilation methods for thermal comfort and energy efficiency. This keyword often intersects with discussions on building design, climatic adaptability, and occupant comfort. For example,

incorporating thermally stable materials like concrete or brick can help regulate indoor temperatures, minimising the need for active heating or cooling systems¹³⁸). The second prominent term, computational fluid dynamics (CFD), occurs 461 times, with 709 links and a total link strength of 5553. CFD is a critical tool in the study of natural ventilation, enabling detailed simulations of airflow, temperature distribution and pollutant dispersion within buildings. Its robust presence in this cluster reflects the growing reliance on computational methods to model and predict the performance of ventilation systems under diverse environmental conditions. Notably, CFD's capabilities extend beyond building applications; for instance, it has been used to analyse combustion processes in power generation. Studies on biomass co-firing in power plants demonstrate CFD's ability to evaluate temperature profiles and pollutant emissions, offering transferable insights into indoor air quality and ventilation management in buildings¹¹⁷⁾¹³⁹). The third keyword, air, with 316 occurrences, 751 links, and a total link strength of 411, serves as a broad but essential term connecting various aspects of airflow analysis. It encompasses a discussion on air's movement, quality and thermal properties, linking fundamental studies to applied research in ventilation and energy efficiency.

Cluster 4, represented in yellow and containing 90 items, focuses on more specialised topics, with keywords that intersect ventilation with areas such as environmental factors, agriculture and animal-related studies. The top three keywords in this cluster – ventilation rate, animals and agriculture- indicate a research focus on applying ventilation systems in various environmental and agricultural contexts. The most prominent keyword in cluster 4 is ventilation rate, with 116 occurrences, 462 links and a total link strength of 1439. This term is crucial in studies that measure the effectiveness of ventilation systems regarding the amount of air exchanged within the space. It often relates to indoor air quality, energy efficiency and occupant comfort, focusing on determining optimal ventilation rates for different building types and usage conditions. The second key term, animals, appears 62 times with 317 links and a total link strength of 964. This term likely connects to studies on how the ventilation system impacts animal welfare, particularly in agricultural settings or livestock housing. Proper ventilation is critical in controlling the indoor environment for animals, helping to maintain air quality and temperature and reduce the spread of diseases or pollutants. The third keyword, agriculture, occurs 53 times with 300 links and a total link strength of 759. Research under this theme explores the application of ventilation in agricultural buildings such as barns, greenhouses, and crop storage facilities. Adequate ventilation in these settings ensures healthy air quality for

crops and livestock, enhancing productivity and sustainability. For example, solar air heaters equipped with automatic control systems can boost thermal efficiency by approximately 39.5%, ensuring stable air temperatures regardless of fluctuations in solar radiation. Such innovations underscore the importance of ventilation in supporting agricultural processes, from crop drying to livestock care¹⁴⁰).

Cluster 5, represented in purple, contains 23 items and focuses on themes related to indoor air quality (IAQ), mechanical ventilation systems and overall ventilation system design. The top three keywords – indoor air quality, mechanical ventilation and ventilation system- highlight the importance of air management technologies in maintaining healthy indoor environments. The leading keyword in this cluster, indoor air quality (IAQ), appears 281 times, with 680mlinks and a total link strength of 3641. IAQ is a central concern in building occupants' health, comfort, and health studies. This term connects with various factors such as pollutant levels, humidity, temperature and airflow, all of which contribute to the overall air quality within a space; the frequent appearance of IAQ in cluster 5 reflects a strong focus on understanding and improving air quality through different ventilation strategies. The second key term, mechanical ventilation, occurs 148 times with 511 links and a total link strength of 1,893. This keyword emphasises the role of active ventilation systems, such as fans, ducts and heat recovery units, in controlling indoor environments. Mechanical ventilation is often combined with or as an alternative to natural ventilation methods. Especially in buildings with insufficient passive airflow to meet thermal comfort and air quality needs. The third keyword, ventilation systems, appears 126 times with 503 links and a total link strength of 1567. This term encompasses various systems designed to provide adequate airflow in buildings, including mechanical and natural ventilation strategies. It ties together multiple studies and approaches to improve air circulation, energy efficiency and overall occupant health in indoor places. Residential habitats are crucial for indoor air quality (IAQ)¹⁴¹⁾¹⁴²). Several studies have focused on the occupants' satisfaction perception of outdoor environmental quality (OEQ) in low-cost, flat housing¹⁴³), as well as indoor environmental quality (IEQ) in low-cost flats¹⁴⁴). Building location, layout, ventilation, finishing materials, occupant activities, and demography significantly influence IAQ in residential dwelling¹⁴⁵⁾¹⁴⁶). The general search reveals a diverse range of studies exploring how natural ventilation can be integrated into residential designs to address both modern challenges and traditional architectural values, strongly emphasising sustainability, energy efficiency, and occupant comfort.

in publications from 2017 indicates a significant academic shift towards exploring sustainable building practices that integrate NV. This aligns with growing concerns over climate change and the search for sustainable architectural solutions that draw on traditional knowledge and vernacular architecture. This recent upturn in research can be attributed to several factors. As global environmental challenges, such as climate change and sustainability, have gained more attention, there has been increasing recognition of the value of traditional knowledge and vernacular architecture, particularly with natural ventilation, suggesting that these approaches may become central to future architectural innovations. This growing body of research could lead to new design guidelines that bridge the gap between modern sustainability goals and traditional architectural wisdom.

Fig. 8: Document by year for focused search

Table 2: Top 10 highly cited on the refined and focused search.

Title	Journal	Cited	Ref.	Main Findings/ Contributions	Thematic Categories
A review on natural ventilation applications through building façade components and ventilation openings in tropical climates	Energy and Buildings (2015)	214	¹⁴⁷⁾	Reviews natural ventilation strategies for tropical climates, emphasizing the role of building façade and ventilation openings. Key elements for future application include ventilation shafts, window to wall ratio and building orientation.	Natural ventilation
A review on windcatcher for passive cooling and natural ventilation in buildings, Part 1: Indoor air quality and thermal comfort assessment	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews (2017)	176	¹⁴⁸⁾	Reviews windcatcher performance in enhancing indoor air quality and thermal comfort. Windcatcher are effective, especially when combined with other cooling methods like evaporating cooling and night ventilation.	Natural ventilation windcatcher
Bioclimatism and vernacular architecture of north-east India	Building and Environment (2009)	150	¹⁴⁹⁾	Investigates the role of bioclimatic principles in vernacular architecture. Highlights the use of passive features such as natural ventilation, insulation, and locally sourced materials in reducing energy consumption.	Natural ventilation Traditional/vernacular
CFD simulation of cross-ventilation in buildings using rooftop windcatchers: impact of outlet openings	Renewable Energy (2018)	140	¹⁵⁰⁾	Uses CFD simulations to analyse cross-ventilation performance with rooftop windcatchers. Finds that outlet placement significantly affects airflow, with one-sided windcatchers being more efficient than two-sided models.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher
The effect of passive measures on thermal comfort and energy conservation. A case study of the hot summer and cold winter climate in the Yangtze River region	Journal of Building Engineering (2018)	139	¹⁵¹⁾	Assesses passive design strategies for improving thermal comfort and reducing energy use in hot summer and cold winter climates. Identifies building orientation, insulation, and natural ventilation as key factors for energy conservation.	Natural ventilation
Experimental study on natural ventilation performance of one-sided wind catcher	Building and Environment (2008)	128	¹⁵²⁾	Experiments with windcatchers demonstrate the wind direction and outlet openings greatly impact ventilation effectiveness. Found that one sided windcatchers are more	Natural ventilation Windcatcher

				efficient in areas with prevailing winds.	
Experimental assessment of the impact of natural ventilation on indoor air quality and thermal comfort conditions of educational buildings in the eastern mediterranean region during the heating period	Journal of Building Engineering (2019)	116	¹⁵³⁾	Investigates natural ventilation in schools, emphasizing its role in thermal comfort and air quality. Finds that certain window and ventilation patterns improve air quality while minimizing heat loss in winter.	Natural ventilation
Impact of different thermal comfort models on zero energy residential buildings in hot climate	Energy and Buildings (2015)	110	¹⁵⁴⁾	Compares thermal comfort models for zero-energy buildings in hot climates. Identifies the most effective consumption and improving comfort during hot period.	Natural ventilation
Modeling energy efficiency of bioclimatic buildings	Energy and Buildings (2005)	110	¹⁵⁵⁾	Develops a regression model to assess energy efficiency in bioclimatic buildings. Finds that passive features like natural ventilation and thermal storage walls contribute to energy efficiency but may not always be beneficial.	Natural ventilation
An adaptive approach to define thermal comfort zones on psychometric chart for naturally ventilated buildings in composite climate of India	Building and Environment (2016)	104	¹⁵⁶⁾	Proposes new comfort zones specific to the composite climate of India. Finds that naturally ventilated buildings can achieve comfort at higher temperature than international standards, with airspeed playing a critical role.	Natural ventilation

Table 2 highlights the contributions of highly cited papers focusing on thematic categories of natural ventilation, vernacular houses and windcatchers, particularly in applying natural ventilation and passive cooling strategies. These papers, predominantly published in renowned journals such as *Energy and Buildings*, *Building and Environment*, and *Renewable Energy*, emphasise the importance of integrating natural ventilation strategies in buildings to enhance indoor air quality, reduce energy consumption, and improve occupant comfort. A significant focus is placed on the performance of natural ventilation systems in tropical, hot, and composite climates. Among the passive strategies explored, windcatchers stand out for their effectiveness in improving indoor air quality and thermal comfort. These traditional architectural elements harness and direct wind into buildings, which is pivotal in promoting natural airflow. Research has shown that when integrated with evaporative cooling systems, windcatchers can maintain thermal comfort under high cooling loads while reducing energy consumption by up to 50% compared to conventional systems²⁹⁾¹⁵⁷⁾. They are particularly effective in hot climates where cross-ventilation is crucial for indoor comfort. However, windcatchers face challenges in colder climates, where

heat loss and potential occupant discomfort may occur. Addressing these issues requires implementing control strategies and integrating windcatchers with heat recovery systems to balance ventilation and thermal performance effectively¹⁵⁸⁾. The use of CFD simulations and experimental assessments further underscores the growing reliance on advanced simulation tools to optimise building design and performance. Table 1 and Table 2 highlight the pivotal role of natural ventilation in enhancing building performance, particularly regarding thermal comfort and energy efficiency. However, they approach the topic from complementary perspectives. Table 1 focuses on applying advanced simulation tools such as CFD, BIM and LCA to assess ventilation performance and optimise sustainable building practices. These tools provide a data-driven framework to model, evaluate, and refine ventilation systems, ensuring energy efficiency and thermal comfort are achieved in diverse building contexts. In contrast, Table 2 delves into the practical applications of passive design strategies, emphasising vernacular architecture and traditional building techniques. Elements such as building façades, ventilation openings, and windcatchers are explored for their effectiveness in

improving natural airflow and cooling, particularly in climates with extreme temperature variations or where energy efficiency is paramount. This research highlights the adaptability of traditional ventilation systems, showing how they can be reimagined within modern sustainable infrastructure. Integrating these traditional strategies into contemporary designs is essential for advancing Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By blending traditional techniques with innovative simulation tools, buildings can reduce energy consumption and improve environmental resilience. This approach fosters a sustainable balance between cultural heritage and modern performance standards, contributing to a greener, more sustainable future¹⁵⁹).

Both tables highlight the intersection of sustainability and indoor comfort, illustrating the potential of natural ventilation systems in reducing environmental impacts and achieving optimal living conditions for building occupants. The combined insights from both tables contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of how traditional and modern approaches to natural ventilation can be integrated into designing energy-efficient and sustainable buildings.

4.4. Assessment of research clusters: Refined search

Fig. 9: VOSviewer analysis for refined search

The VOSviewer analysis in Figure 9, with a minimal occurrence threshold of 5, yielded 2422 keywords, of which 176 met the criteria. This analysis identified 6 clusters, each highlighting specific focus areas within the field.

Within cluster 1 (red), comprising 36 items, the emphasis lies on computational techniques and build environment. The keyword building occurring 43 times with a total link strength of 455 and 135 links reflects the broad scope of architectural studies focusing on natural ventilation. The term computational fluid dynamics (CFD), appearing 49 times with a total link strength of 513 and 134 links, highlights the growing reliance on simulation tools to analyse airflow dynamics and optimise designs. Meanwhile, air quality with 33 occurrences, a total link strength of 361 and 119 links points to the importance of

maintaining healthy indoor environments while integrating natural ventilation strategies. These trends illustrate a dynamic interplay between traditional housing features and modern analytical methods, emphasising the pursuit of sustainability and comfort in architectural research.

Cluster 2 (green), consisting of 30 items, emphasises energy performance and architectural strategies for enhancing natural ventilation. The keyword energy efficiency emerges with 57 occurrences, 142 links and a total link strength of 542, reflecting its centrality in sustainable housing design. Architectural design follows closely with 54 occurrences, 134 links and a total link strength of 507, showcasing its significance in shaping effective ventilation systems. Thermal performance, with 25 occurrences, 94 links, and a total link strength of 209, highlights the importance of assessing how traditional and vernacular housing features regulate indoor temperature.

Cluster 3 (blue), also with 30 items, focuses on core concepts of ventilation and comfort in housing. Ventilation, the most prominent keyword, appears 235 times with 175 links and a total line strength of 2046, emphasising its overarching role in the analysis. Thermal comfort, with 119 occurrences, 167 links and a total link strength of 949, underscores the need to balance airflow with occupants' well-being. Housing, which appears 57 times, links with 133 items and has a total link strength of 530, reflecting the domain's emphasis on natural ventilation applications in residential settings.

Cluster 4 (yellow), comprising 29 items, delves into passive strategies and vernacular architectural approaches. The keyword vernacular architecture, with 50 occurrences, 115 links, and a total link strength of 358, highlights traditional housing designs' cultural and environmental adaptability. Passive cooling, occurring 35 times with 120 links and a total link strength of 331, emphasises strategies to reduce energy consumption naturally. Indoor air, appearing 25 times, links with 102 items and has a total link strength of 280, pointing to the relevance of maintaining air quality through natural means.

Cluster 5 (purple), containing 26 items, focuses on energy systems and broader architectural themes. Energy utilisation, with 53 occurrences, 152 links, and a total link strength of 569, reflects the integration of efficient energy use in ventilation systems. Heating, which appears 33 times, connects with 122 links and a total link strength of 322, indicating the interplay of heating and ventilation in traditional housing. Architecture, occurring 28 times with 89 links and a total link strength of 225, emphasises the design aspects of natural ventilation.

Cluster 6 Cluster 6 (light blue), with 25 items, emphasises natural ventilation and related cooling techniques. Natural ventilation, the second most frequent keyword overall, appears 185 times with 174 links and a total link strength of 1481, reaffirming its importance in sustainable design. Computational fluid dynamics (CFD) follows with 49

4.6. Targeted Search

The targeted search for TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (traditional OR folk OR Indigenous) AND (vernacular AND house) AND (windcatcher OR woodcarving OR latticework OR mashrabiya OR Kumiko) revealed an interesting temporal distribution of 53 documents shown in Figure 11. In 2023, there was a notable peak with 11 publications, followed by 10 papers in 2024, indicating a surge in research activity. 2020 and 2022 saw moderate engagement, with 6 and 5 documents published, respectively. There were 4 documents each in 2017, 2018, and 2021, showing consistent but less intense focus during those years. Earlier years, such as 2014 and 2021, had 2 publications each, while 2013 and 2016 had only 1 document.

Interestingly, the absence of publications in 2015 highlights a lull in academic interest. However, by 2023, there has been a growing acknowledgement of architectural elements such as windcatchers, woodcarving, latticework, mashrabiya, and Kumiko in enhancing natural ventilation, particularly in traditional and vernacular houses. Windcatchers, originating from Persian and Egyptian civilisations, exemplify this trend. Widely used in Middle Eastern architecture, these structures have been shown to significantly reduce energy consumption and improve thermal comfort in both multi-story and residential buildings. In regions like Şanlıurfa, Turkey, and Hyderabad, Pakistan, they are called Badgirs or Manghs, reflecting their cultural and regional significances¹⁶⁸⁾¹⁶⁹⁾¹⁷⁰⁾. Similarly, woodcarving and latticework, often seen in traditional Malay and Middle Eastern architecture, serve

decorative and functional purposes. For instance, perforated Malay carving windows enhance air velocity within living spaces, improving thermal comfort and energy efficiency¹⁷¹⁾. Mashrabiya, characterised by intricate wooden latticework sometimes adorned with stained glass, is another architectural feature that enhances ventilation and cooling while providing privacy¹⁷²⁾. Kumiko, a Japanese woodworking technique, represents another innovative approach to natural ventilation. This method involves assembling wooden pieces without nails, resulting in intricate patterns often used in screens and partitions. Renowned for its precision, Kumiko allows fresh air flow while reducing reliance on mechanical cooling systems¹⁷³⁾. Collectively, these architectural elements demonstrate their ability to create sustainable and comfortable indoor environments by promoting natural ventilation and reducing energy dependence.

Fig. 11: Documents by year for a targeted search

Table 3: Top 10 highly cited for a targeted search

Title	Journal	Cited	Ref.	Main Findings/ Contributions	Thematic Categories
A review on windcatcher for passive cooling and natural ventilation in buildings, Part 1: Indoor air quality and thermal comfort assessment	Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews (2017)	177	¹⁴⁸⁾	Windcatchers effectively improve indoor air quality (IAQ) and thermal comfort, particularly in hot and temperate climates, by manipulating pressure differences and buoyancy effects. Incorporating additional cooling methods like evaporative cooling, earth-to-air heat exchangers (EAHE), and heat transfer devices (HTD) alongside night ventilation is essential for maintaining comfort in hot climates.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher
CFD simulation of cross-ventilation in buildings using rooftop wind-catchers: Impact of outlet openings	Renewable Energy (2018)	141	¹⁵⁰⁾	Using outlet openings close to the wind catcher does not increase induced airflow and can significantly reduce indoor air quality. A combination of a one-sided wind-catcher and window provides superior ventilation performance, while two-sided wind-catchers lead to the lowest indoor air quality and air change efficiency.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher
The potential influence of building optimization and passive design strategies on natural ventilation systems in	Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology (2019)	53	¹⁷⁴⁾	Combining optimization methods with passive design strategies is effective in improving the Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) of underground buildings, potentially reducing energy consumption and enhancing thermal comfort.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional

underground buildings: The state of the art				Incorporating natural ventilation and utilizing soil in building design can reduce the energy consumption of underground buildings, contributing to energy efficiency while maintaining acceptable IEQ levels.	
Natural ventilation by windcatcher (Badgir): A review on the impacts of geometry, microclimate and macroclimate	Energy and Buildings (2020)	50	¹⁷⁵⁾	Windcatchers with a square cross-section and curved roof perform better in ventilating rooms compared to other configurations. The integration of windcatchers with other passive systems, like solar chimneys and wing walls, significantly enhances ventilation efficiency.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional
What can we learn from Malay vernacular houses?	Sustainable Cities and Society (2014)	47	¹⁷⁶⁾	The study highlights that many Malay inhabitants still prefer living in houses that reflect traditional values due to their alignment with local environmental characteristics and daily functions. Privacy, optimal space use, and natural ventilation are essential in enhancing the quality of life within the context of vernacular Malay houses.	Natural ventilation Vernacular/traditional
The role of traditional Lattice window Mashrabiya in delivering single-sided ventilation-A CFD Study	Architectural Science Review (2013)	43	¹⁷⁷⁾	The study demonstrates that wind towers can enhance the ventilation efficiency in buildings, increasing indoor air velocity by 63%. CFD simulations reveal that wind towers significantly improve airflow distribution inside buildings, particularly in hot and arid climates like the Middle East.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional
Functionalism of wind renewable energy in vernacular elements of wind catcher and moshabak (Case study: Qrshn island)	Sustainability (Switzerland) (2017)	40	¹⁷⁸⁾	The study emphasizes the use of wind-induced ventilation systems in the vernacular architecture of Sistan, particularly the unique design elements such as roofs and ventilator openings. CFD simulations provide insights into the airflow behaviour and ventilation performance, recommending optimal room orientations to maximize natural ventilation.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional
Numerical investigation of evaporative cooling strategies on the aerothermal performance of courtyard buildings in hot-dry climates	Energy and Buildings (2020)	36	¹⁷⁹⁾	The study finds that closed Mashrabiya reduce the flow of hot air and maintain indoor temperatures between 35.4–35.8 °C during the afternoon. Opening the Mashrabiya enhances airflow but does not significantly impact comfort during the midday; however, night cooling is improved. Integration of passive cooling strategies, such as wetted cloth near the Mashrabiya inlet, provides the most effective cooling, offering comfort during the early morning hours	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional
The consequence of combining indigenous technique with a flexible design to reduce energy consumption in residential buildings for future architect	Energy and Buildings (2018)	34	¹⁸⁰⁾	The study shows that four-sided wind towers primarily function as heat dissipation devices rather than inducing outdoor breezes, especially in hot-arid regions of Iran. The performance of wind towers in relation to wind incident angles reveals that they are most effective at extracting air out of buildings for 61.5% of wind directions.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher Vernacular/traditional

The effect of onset turbulent flows on ventilation with a two-sided rooftop windcatcher	Energy and Built Environment (2022)	32 ¹⁸¹⁾	The review finds that the efficiency of windcatchers is significantly influenced by parameters such as height, configuration, and cross-section. A one-sided windcatcher is most effective in regions with a consistent wind direction, while other configurations perform better in areas with variable winds.	Natural ventilation Windcatcher
---	-------------------------------------	--------------------	--	------------------------------------

Table 3 further expands on the themes discussed in Table 1 and Table 2, offering a more focused understanding of how traditional architectural elements can enhance natural ventilation, IAQ, and thermal comfort in modern sustainable architecture. While Table 1 emphasises the integration of advanced simulation tools such as CFD and BIM to optimise building performance, Table 3 focuses on highly cited papers that specifically address the role of passive cooling strategies and vernacular architectural elements in promoting energy efficiency, thermal comfort and sustainability.

Furthermore, Table 2 provides an overview of studies focusing on passive design strategies, particularly in warm climates, highlighting bioclimatic design principles and natural ventilation. The studies in Table 3 align with this by investigating how vernacular elements—like the traditional lattice windows or windcatchers—serve as passive systems, enhancing natural ventilation without needing mechanical interventions. These studies contribute further to the growing body of work emphasising the role of energy efficiency and sustainability through adopting time-tested vernacular techniques, which resonate with the conclusions in Table 2 about the environmental and resource-conscious benefits of passive design.

Thus, Table 3 effectively ties together the findings from Table 1 and Table 2, reinforcing that traditional architectural features can improve indoor comfort and support sustainable, energy-efficient design strategies when combined with modern simulation tools. Table 3 showcases the evolution of design practices that blend heritage with contemporary computational methods to address environmental and comfort challenges in modern architecture.

4.7. Assessment of research clusters: targeted search

For a targeted search shown in Figure 12, the analysis identifies 172 keywords, with 7 meeting the threshold of a minimum of 5 occurrences. These keywords are grouped into two distinct clusters, reflecting their thematic and contextual relationships.

Cluster 1 (red, 5 items) focuses on concepts related to natural ventilation and its associated strategies. The keywords “natural ventilation” emerges as the most significant in this cluster, with 30 occurrences, 6 links and

a total link strength of 36, underscoring its centrality in the research. “wind tower” and “passive cooling” are also prominent, with 7 and 8 occurrences, respectively. Their link strength, 18 for wind tower and 16 for passive cooling”. Passive strategies such as wind towers are particularly noteworthy in this context. By capturing wind from higher altitudes and directing it into buildings, wind towers facilitate natural ventilation, improving indoor air quality without relying on mechanical systems. This approach enhances occupant comfort and significantly reduces energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to more sustainable architectural practices. Similarly, passive cooling techniques optimise thermal performance by leveraging natural environmental conditions, reducing energy-intensive mechanical systems' ne. This cluster's emphasis on these strategies illustrates their pivotal role in promoting sustainable building practices, aligning with contemporary energy efficiency goals and environmental responsibility^{182) 183)}.

Cluster 2 (Green, 2 items) emphasises traditional and simulation-based approaches. “Vernacular architecture” plays a key role, appearing 9 times with 5 links and a link strength of 10, illustrating its pivotal role in simulating and optimising natural ventilation systems.

Fig. 12: VOSviewer analysis for a targeted search

These clusters provide insights into the interplay between traditional architectural principles and modern simulation techniques, highlighting their combined impact on improving indoor environment quality and energy efficiency. Combining traditional passive concepts with modern simulation techniques can significantly reduce energy consumption. For instance, simulations have shown

that incorporating conventional design elements into modern buildings can lower energy demand and improve thermal comfort^{184) 185)}.

5. Limitation of study

The study's findings provide valuable insights into the environmental evaluation of natural ventilation in traditional houses, yet certain limitations constrain them. A key limitation is the reliance solely on bibliometric data from the Scopus database, which may result in excluding pertinent publications not indexed within this platform. For instance, the search term TITLE-ABS-KEY (natural AND ventilation) AND (traditional OR folk OR Indigenous) AND (vernacular AND house) AND (windcatcher OR woodcarving OR latticework OR mashrabiya OR Kumiko) returned only 53 documents in Scopus, despite the apparent relevance of the topic. This limitation is further emphasised by the restricted scope of Scopus, which may only partially represent the breadth of research available in this area. Scopus's journal field classifications can be misleading, as they do not always accurately reflect the content of the journals. This is particularly problematic for cross-field and specialist journals, where the classification may not align with the research topics covered^{190) 191)}.

In contrast, a Google Scholar search using the exact words produced about 6,720 results, revealing a broader range of publications. Google Scholar provides citation metrics, enabling users to track how often a paper has been cited, which can help assess the impact of research^{192) 193)}. This discrepancy highlights¹⁹¹⁾ the potential volume of literature not visible in Scopus searches. However, it is essential to note that Google Scholar includes a mix of peer-reviewed and non-peer-reviewed sources and aggregates content beyond titles, abstracts, and keywords. This distinction between databases further complicates the direct comparison of results and suggests that certain publications may not be as rigorously vetted as those found in Scopus. These findings emphasise the importance of utilising multiple databases and refining keyword strategies to understand the research landscape comprehensively.

Future research should consider broader search methodologies to overcome these limitations and provide a more exhaustive field analysis. By combining results from different platforms, researchers can better capture the diversity of research on a given topic, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding. Future research could also explore the integration of additional search parameters, such as publication type or research methodology, to better filter relevant publications and ensure a more robust review.

6. Discussion

This study investigates the role of traditional architectural

elements, particularly those related to natural ventilation, in improving indoor comfort, energy efficiency, and sustainability in contemporary architecture. The research demonstrates a clear connection between vernacular features like windcatchers, woodcarvings, latticework, and other passive cooling systems and the growing body of literature emphasising their importance in modern sustainable design. The data analysis from the targeted search shows a notable increase in research interest, particularly in 2023 and 2024, with 53 documents identified across various themes, such as natural ventilation, windcatcher, and vernacular or traditional architectural elements. This shows that while there is existing research on the intersection of natural ventilation and traditional architectural elements, there is room for further exploration in integrating these features into contemporary housing or examining their performance in various climates, as shown in Figure 13.

Fig. 13: Process of Narrowing the Literature Search

One key finding from the targeted search analysis is the shift in research trends toward understanding how traditional elements, like windcatchers and woodcarvings, can enhance natural ventilation in buildings without relying on mechanical systems. Windcatchers, for example, have been shown to significantly reduce energy consumption while improving thermal comfort in regions such as the Middle East and South Asia. Windcatchers support energy efficiency and preserve cultural heritage, making them a viable solution for modern sustainable architecture in areas with the traditional use of these systems¹⁹⁴⁾. Studies investigating the effects of traditional lattice windows or Kumiko designs further highlight the potential of these elements in optimising air movement and reducing reliance on air conditioning systems. The bibliometric analysis reveals a concentration of research in

the last few years, with the increasing integration of computational tools such as CFD and BIM to simulate and optimise these passive systems. The synergy between traditional architectural knowledge and modern simulation techniques allows for blending time-tested solutions with cutting-edge technology to create more sustainable and energy-efficient buildings. These insights point to a growing recognition of the importance of passive design in addressing contemporary environmental challenges, including reducing carbon footprints and improving indoor air quality (IAQ) in urban environments.

However, the study also highlights the limitations inherent in the bibliometric approach, particularly the reliance on Scopus for gathering data. While Scopus is a highly respected database compared to other platforms like Google Scholar, its limited scope may have excluded relevant publications that could further enrich the discussion^{195) 196)}.¹⁹⁶⁾This discrepancy suggests that future research could benefit from a broader approach, utilising multiple databases and refining search strategies to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the literature.

Additionally, although there is significant potential in adopting traditional elements, further research is needed to explore how these elements can be incorporated into modern construction practices, particularly in regions with varying climatic conditions. Future studies could explore integrating traditional passive systems with new materials and technologies, offering more diverse approaches to sustainable architecture.

7. Conclusion

This study underscores the significant role that traditional architectural elements play in enhancing natural ventilation, thermal comfort, and energy efficiency in buildings. The rising number of publications in the last few years signals a growing recognition of the value of vernacular architecture in addressing contemporary environmental and sustainability challenges. Elements such as windcatchers, woodcarvings, and latticework provide effective, low-cost passive cooling solutions that can reduce dependence on mechanical systems, improve IAQ, and lower energy consumption in both residential and commercial buildings.

The findings highlight the importance of integrating traditional knowledge with modern simulation tools like CFD and BIM to optimise building performance. This hybrid approach, combining the wisdom of vernacular designs with the precision of computational methods, offers a promising path toward more sustainable and comfortable living environments. The literature also points to the potential of passive cooling strategies as an essential component of bioclimatic design, particularly in warm climates, which aligns with global sustainability goals.

Despite the valuable insights presented, the study

acknowledges limitations regarding database selection and excluding certain publications. To address this, future research should incorporate broader search methodologies, explore integrating traditional passive strategies with modern technologies, and consider using multiple databases for more comprehensive field analyses. By overcoming these limitations, future studies can further advance our understanding of how traditional architectural elements can contribute to sustainable architecture in the 21st century.

In conclusion, the study affirms that traditional architectural features can be crucial in creating energy-efficient, environmentally responsible, and culturally rich buildings when paired with modern simulation tools and technologies. These findings lay the groundwork for further exploration into how traditional designs can be adapted and integrated into contemporary architecture, providing sustainable solutions for future generations.

Acknowledgements

We want to extend our appreciation to the Tempus Public Foundation for granting the opportunity to receive the Stipendium Hungaricum Scholarship for the doctoral program. We also want to express our gratitude to the reviewers who have provided constructive feedback.

References

- 1) K.T. Zingre, X. Yang, and M.P. Wan, "Performance analysis of cool roof, green roof and thermal insulation on a concrete flat roof in tropical climate," *Evergreen*, 2 (2) (2015). doi:10.5109/1544078.
- 2) D. Valechha, A. Patil, S. Rayalu, Y. Teraoka, and N. Labhsetwar, "Improved oxygen carriers for cleaner energy generation through chemical looping combustion," *Evergreen*, 4 (2011).
- 3) A. Pal, K. Uddin, K. Thu, and B.B. Saha, "Environmental assessment and characteristics of next generation refrigerants," *Evergreen*, 5 (2) (2018). doi:10.5109/1936218.
- 4) L.A. Al-Azez Mahdi, M.A. Fayad, and M.T. Chaichan, "Analysis of entropy generation for horizontal heated cylinder by natural convection and radiation," *Evergreen*, 10 (2) (2023). doi:10.5109/6792884.
- 5) S. Agarwal, M. Tyagi, and R.K. Garg, "Circular economy reinforcement to diminish GHG emissions: a grey dematel approach," *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6781099.
- 6) S. Notosiswoyo, and I. Iskandar, "Contribution of coal mine and coal-fired power plant to CO₂-emission in Indonesia," *Journal of Novel Carbon Resource Sciences*, 4 (2011).
- 7) M. Kalsia, A. Sharma, R. Kaushik, and R.S. Dondapati, "Evaporative cooling technologies:

- conceptual review study,” *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6781102.
- 8) B. Shahriari, A. Hassanpoor, A. Navehebrahim, and S. Jafarinia, “A systematic review of green human resource management,” *Evergreen*, 6 (2) (2019). doi:10.5109/2328408.
 - 9) D. Singh, and A. Singh, “Role of building automation technology in creating a smart and sustainable built environment,” *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6781101.
 - 10) S. Chaturvedi, “Energy efficiency and sustainability in buildings,” in: *Proceedings of the AEI 2008 Conference - AEI 2008: Building Integration Solutions*, 2008. doi:10.1061/41002(328)59.
 - 11) Y.D. Herlambang, Supriyo, B. Prasetyo, A.S. Alfauzi, T. Prasetyo, Marliyati, and F. Arifin, “Experimental and simulation investigation on savonius turbine: influence of inlet-outlet ratio using a modified blade shaped to improve performance,” *Evergreen*, 9 (2) (2022). doi:10.5109/4794172.
 - 12) Y.D. Herlambang, Supriyo, B. Prasetyo, A.S. Alfauzi, T. Prasetyo, Marliyati, and F. Arifin, “Experimental and simulation investigation on savonius turbine: influence of inlet-outlet ratio using a modified blade shaped to improve performance,” *Evergreen*, 9 (2) (2022). doi:10.5109/4794172.
 - 13) A.F. Pachman, D.H. Didane, Wijianto, M. Al-Ghriybah, N.F. Nasir, S. Al-Alimi, and B. Manshoor, “A study of global solar radiations measurement in java island, Indonesia,” *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6781071.
 - 14) M. Al-Ghriybah, “Assessment of wind energy potentiality at ajloun, Jordan using Weibull distribution function,” *Evergreen*, 9 (1) (2022). doi:10.5109/4774211.
 - 15) N.A. Pambudi, V.S. Pramudita, M.K. Biddinika, and S. Jalilinasrabad, “So close yet so far - how people in the vicinity of potential sites respond to geothermal energy power generation: an evidence from Indonesia,” *Evergreen*, 9 (1) (2022). doi:10.5109/4774210.
 - 16) M. Muslihudin, W.R. Adawiyah, E. Hendarto, R.D. Megasari, and M.F. Ramadhan, “Environmental constraints in building process a sustainable geothermal power plant on the slopes of Slamet Mount, central java, Indonesia,” *Evergreen*, 9 (2) (2022). doi:10.5109/4793669.
 - 17) B. Pranoto, I. Adilla, H. Soekarno, N.K. Supriatna, Adrian, L. Efiyanti, D.A. Indrawan, N.W. Hesty, and S.R. Fithri, “Using satellite data of palm oil area for potential utilization in calculating palm oil trunk waste as cofiring fuel biomass,” *Evergreen*, 10 (3) (2023). doi:10.5109/7151728.
 - 18) R.K. Ahmad, S.A. Sulaiman, A.M.B.A. Majid, S. Yusuf, S.S. Dol, M. Inayat, and H.A. Umar, “Assessing the technical and environmental potential of coconut shell biomass: experimental study through pyrolysis and gasification,” *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6782165.
 - 19) A.M.M. Ismaiel, and S. Yoshida, “Study of turbulence intensity effect on the fatigue lifetime of wind turbines,” *Evergreen*, 5 (1) 25–32 (2018). doi:10.5109/1929727.
 - 20) Safril, Mustofa, M. Zen, F. Sumasto, and M. Wirandi, “Design of cooling system on brushless dc motor to improve heat transfers efficiency,” *Evergreen*, 9 (2) (2022). doi:10.5109/4794206.
 - 21) A. Mohammed, A. Mustapha, and N. Mu’azu, “Energy efficient buildings as a tool for ensuring sustainability in the building industry,” 2011 International Conference on Multimedia Technology, ICMT 2011, (2011). doi:10.1109/ICMT.2011.6003238.
 - 22) M.G. Chaudhary, N. Kumar, and S. Kumar, “Future prospect of plumbene: a review,” *Evergreen*, 8 (4) (2021). doi:10.5109/4742116.
 - 23) N. Nurwidiana, B.M. Sopha, and A. Widyaparaga, “Modelling photovoltaic system adoption for households: a systematic literature review,” *Evergreen*, 8 (1) (2021). doi:10.5109/4372262.
 - 24) R.A. Rouf, M.A. Hakim Khan, K.M. Ariful Kabir, and B.B. Saha, “Energy management and heat storage for solar adsorption cooling,” *Evergreen*, 3 (2) (2016). doi:10.5109/1800866.
 - 25) Z. Tong, Y. Chen, A. Malkawi, Z. Liu, and R.B. Freeman, “Energy saving potential of natural ventilation in China: the impact of ambient air pollution,” *Appl Energy*, 179 660–668 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.07.019.
 - 26) M. Ohba, R. Yoshie, and I. Lun, “Review of recent natural ventilation research study in Japan,” *Development*, (2005).
 - 27) Y. Wang, F.Y. Zhao, J. Kuckelkorn, D. Liu, J. Liu, and J.L. Zhang, “Classroom energy efficiency and air environment with displacement natural ventilation in a passive public school building,” *Energy Build*, 70 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2013.11.071.
 - 28) M. Belhous, M. Boumhaout, S. Oukach, and H. Hamdi, “Effect of a material based on date palm fibers on the thermal behavior of a residential building in the atlantic climate of morocco,” *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15 (7) (2023). doi:10.3390/su15076314.
 - 29) D.P. Sari, A. Sumarno, A.M. Prasetyo, Maidina, and L.N. Ngeljaratan, “Energy conservation techniques in tropical climate - a comprehensive review and adaptation of the lamin house for nusantara,” *Evergreen*, 10 (3) (2023). doi:10.5109/7151769.
 - 30) M.K. Gupta, “Simulating the fluid flow via ceiling

- diffuser using openfoam,” *Evergreen*, 10 (1) (2023). doi:10.5109/6781100.
- 31) D. Aviv, K.W. Chen, E. Teitelbaum, D. Sheppard, J. Pantelic, A. Rysanek, and F. Meggers, “A fresh (air) look at ventilation for COVID-19: estimating the global energy savings potential of coupling natural ventilation with novel radiant cooling strategies,” *Appl Energy*, 292 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.116848.
 - 32) T. Ahmed, P. Kumar, and L. Mottet, “Natural ventilation in warm climates: the challenges of thermal comfort, heatwave resilience and indoor air quality,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 138 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.rser.2020.110669.
 - 33) P. Moscoso-García, and F. Quesada-Molina, “Analysis of passive strategies in traditional vernacular architecture,” *Buildings*, 13 (8) (2023). doi:10.3390/buildings13081984.
 - 34) Y. Zou, J. Guo, D. Xia, S. Lou, Y. Huang, X. Yang, and Z. Zhong, “Quantitative analysis and enhancement on passive survivability of vernacular houses in the hot and humid region of china,” *Journal of Building Engineering*, 71 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.jobe.2023.106431.
 - 35) C. Berbouche, L. Sriti, and S. Latreche, “Vernacular features in rural housing of the aurassien massif between traditional practices and bioclimatic aspect. case study of ain zaatout (algeria),” *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 39 (2023). doi:10.47577/tssj.v39i1.8281.
 - 36) S. Martinovic, N. Zecevic, and A. Salihbegović, “Vernacular residential architecture in the context of sustainability - case study of svrzo’s house complex,” *Journal of Sustainable Architecture and Civil Engineering*, 32 (1) (2023). doi:10.5755/j01.sace.32.1.32753.
 - 37) Z. Lu, J. Xu, W. Gao, C. Hou, and Y. Hao, “A comprehensive effectiveness study of passive design parameters for traditional dwellings in qinba mountainous area,” *Indoor and Built Environment*, 32 (4) (2023). doi:10.1177/1420326X221135069.
 - 38) S. Murtyas, A. Hagishima, and N.H. Kusumaningdyah, “Observed diverse indoor thermal environments of low-cost dwellings located in a kampung district,” *Evergreen*, 8 (1) (2021). doi:10.5109/4372283.
 - 39) S. Schelbach, “Developing a method to improve the energy efficiency of modern buildings by using traditional passive concepts of resource efficiency and climate adaptation,” *International Journal of Sustainable Development and Planning*, 11 (1) (2016). doi:10.2495/SDP-V11-N1-23-38.
 - 40) Ar.E. Verma, and Prof.S. Srivastava, “Role of passive design techniques for a comfortable indoor environment: comparison between tradition & modern architecture in hot climate,” *Int J Res Appl Sci Eng Technol*, 11 (6) (2023). doi:10.22214/ijraset.2023.54444.
 - 41) E. Sorooshnia, P. Rahnamayiezekavat, M. Rashidi, M. Sadeghi, and B. Samali, “Passive intelligent kinetic external dynamic shade design for improving indoor comfort and minimizing energy consumption,” *Buildings*, 13 (4) (2023). doi:10.3390/buildings13041090.
 - 42) G.J. Barea-Paci, C. Ganem-Karlen, M.C. Molina, and P. Mateo, “Efectividad a futuro de las estrategias de diseño pasivas en viviendas,” *Revista Hábitat Sustentable*, 13 (1) (2023). doi:10.22320/07190700.2023.13.01.03.
 - 43) A. Sarkar, and J. Panicker M, “PASSIVE designs and thermal performance of the temples in the warm-humid climatic zone of south india,” *ShodhKosh: Journal of Visual and Performing Arts*, 5 (1) 2361–2382 (2024). doi:10.29121/shodhkosh.v5.i1.2024.2374.
 - 44) K. Mousli, and G. Semprini, “Passive systems in traditional houses in Middle East areas: Solutions and effects of natural ventilation,” in: *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng*, 2019. doi:10.1088/1757-899X/609/3/032056.
 - 45) U. Dietrich, and L.G. Rios, “Passive adaptive strategies for the optimisation of comfort and energy demand in traditional and contemporary buildings in hot, humid climates,” *WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment*, 217 (2018). doi:10.2495/SDP180041.
 - 46) M. Hazbei, O. Nematollahi, M. Behnia, and Z. Adib, “Reduction of energy consumption using passive architecture in hot and humid climates,” *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 47 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.tust.2014.12.001.
 - 47) M. Mohamed, A. Klingmann, and H. Samir, “Examining the thermal performance of vernacular houses in asir region of saudi arabia,” *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 58 (2) 419–428 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.aej.2019.03.004.
 - 48) L. Huang, N. Hamza, B. Lan, and D. Zahi, “Climate-responsive design of traditional dwellings in the cold-arid regions of tibet and a field investigation of indoor environments in winter,” *Energy Build*, 128 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.07.006.
 - 49) A. Sarkar, “Study of climate responsive passive design features in traditional hill architecture of khyah village in hamirpur, himachal pradesh, india for indoor thermal comfort,” *Journal of The Institution of Engineers (India): Series A*, 94 (1) (2013). doi:10.1007/s40030-013-0033-z.
 - 50) M. Isaac, and D.P. van Vuuren, “Modeling global residential sector energy demand for heating and air

- conditioning in the context of climate change,” *Energy Policy*, 37 (2) (2009). doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2008.09.051.
- 51) A. Mastrucci, E. Byers, S. Pachauri, and N.D. Rao, “Improving the sdg energy poverty targets: residential cooling needs in the global south,” *Energy Build*, 186 405–415 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.01.015.
 - 52) International Energy Agency, “The future of cooling – analysis,” IEA, (2022).
 - 53) L.W. Davis, and P.J. Gertler, “Contribution of air conditioning adoption to future energy use under global warming,” *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 112 (19) (2015). doi:10.1073/pnas.1423558112.
 - 54) P. Byrne, N. Putra, T. Maré, N. Abdallah, P. Lalanne, I. Alhamid, P. Estelle, A. Yatim, and A.L. Tiffonnet, “Design of a solar ac system including a pcm storage for sustainable resorts in tropical region,” *Evergreen*, 6 (2) (2019). doi:10.5109/2321009.
 - 55) H. Han, M. Hatta, and H. Rahman, “Smart ventilation for energy conservation in buildings,” *Evergreen*, 6 (1) (2019). doi:10.5109/2321005.
 - 56) F. Savanti, E. Setyowati, and G. Hardiman, “The impact of ventilation on indoor air quality and air change rate,” *Evergreen*, 9 (1) (2022). doi:10.5109/4774237.
 - 57) Z. (John) Zhai, M.H. Johnson, M. El Mankibi, and N. Stathopoulos, “Review of natural ventilation models,” *International Journal of Ventilation*, 15 (3–4) (2016). doi:10.1080/14733315.2016.1214390.
 - 58) D. Bienvenido-Huertas, M.L. de la Hoz-Torres, A.J. Aguilar, B. Tejedor, and D. Sánchez-García, “Holistic overview of natural ventilation and mixed mode in built environment of warm climate zones and hot seasons,” *Build Environ*, 245 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110942.
 - 59) P. Abdo, R. Taghipour, and B.P. Huynh, “Three dimensional simulation of ventilation flow through a solar windcatcher,” in: *ASME-JSME-KSME 2019 8th Joint Fluids Engineering Conference, AJKFluids 2019*, 2019. doi:10.1115/AJKFluids2019-5383.
 - 60) A. L. Muhammad, M. Z. Ringim, and L. A. Isma’il, “Transient investigation of stack-driven airflow process through rectangular cross-ventilated building with two vents in the absence of opposing flow in the upper opening,” *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7 (3) (2018). doi:10.14419/ijet.v7i3.9422.
 - 61) I.A. Wahab, L.H. Ismail, and A. Kadir, “Opening design and position effect on building natural stack effect and cross ventilation,” *International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research*, 5 (5) (2016).
 - 62) E.A. Essah, R. Yao, and A. Short, “Assessing stack ventilation strategies in the continental climate of beijing using cfd simulations,” *International Journal of Ventilation*, 16 (1) (2017). doi:10.1080/14733315.2016.1203609.
 - 63) J.Y. Kim, S.G. Lee, and S.W. Jeon, “Field experiment of the measures to control the stack effect in stairwell of building,” in: *Proceedings of the World Congress on Mechanical, Chemical, and Material Engineering*, 2017. doi:10.11159/htff17.112.
 - 64) P. Mckeen, and Z. Liao, “The influence of building airtightness on airflow in stairwells,” *Buildings*, 9 (10) (2019). doi:10.3390/buildings9100208.
 - 65) T. Pongtaveesap, S. Chirattananon, R.H.B. Exell, and P. Chaiwiwatworakul, “Air flow in a hot water induced stack subject to wind disturbance,” in: *Adv Mat Res*, 2013. doi:10.4028/www.scientific.net/AMR.622-623.1564.
 - 66) I.S. Walker, and D.J. Wilson, “Field validation of algebraic equations for stack and wind driven air infiltration calculations,” *HVAC and R Research*, 4 (2) (1998). doi:10.1080/10789669.1998.10391395.
 - 67) B. Mulyana, A. Polgár, and A. Vityi, “Three decades of forest carbon dynamics modeling using co2fix: a bibliometric analysis,” *Evergreen*, 10 (4) 2105–2119 (2023). doi:10.5109/7160871.
 - 68) R.N. Broadus, “Toward a definition of ‘bibliometrics,’” *Scientometrics*, 12 (5–6) (1987). doi:10.1007/BF02016680.
 - 69) O. Ellegaard, and J.A. Wallin, “The bibliometric analysis of scholarly production: how great is the impact?,” *Scientometrics*, 105 (3) (2015). doi:10.1007/s11192-015-1645-z.
 - 70) M. Bordons, and M.a Ángeles Zulueta, “Evaluación de la actividad científica a través de indicadores bibliométricos,” *Rev Esp Cardiol*, 52 (10) (1999). doi:10.1016/s0300-8932(99)75008-6.
 - 71) S. Sakamoto, “Japan and the Law of the Sea: Key Historical and Contemporary Milestones,” in: 2021. doi:10.1007/978-981-33-6954-2_2.
 - 72) M. Van Der Tempel, I. Wouters, F. Descamps, and D. Aerts, “Ventilation techniques in the 19 th century: Learning from the past,” in: *WIT Transactions on the Built Environment*, 2011. doi:10.2495/STR110231.
 - 73) M. Ismail, A. Malek, A. Rahman, S.N. Kamaruzzaman, and R.A. Razak, “Stack ventilation strategies in architectural context: a brief review of historical development, current trends and future possibilities,” *Ijrras*, 11 (1) (2011).
 - 74) W.L.L.F.Z.C. Jun Yan, “Wind environment simulation based on natural ventilation of traditional large house dwellings in northeast hunan province,” *Academic Journal of Engineering and Technology Science*, 6 (5) (2023). doi:10.25236/AJETS.2023.060501.
 - 75) J.K.P. Ng, “Traditional Ventilation Skills of Lingnan Chinese Architecture – a Case Study of Macau Mandarin’s House,” in: *Lecture Notes in Civil*

- Engineering, 2023. doi:10.1007/978-981-19-4293-8_57.
- 76) T. Gaczoł, "BUILDING ventilation across history – examples," *Space&FORM*, 2022 (49) 211–232 (2022). doi:10.21005/pif.2022.49.E-02.
- 77) Y. Hou, A. Li, and S. Mei, "Learning from chinese traditional architecture: field test and cfd modelling of ventilation enhancement techniques in southern chinese houses," *International Journal of Ventilation*, 21 (1) (2022). doi:10.1080/14733315.2021.1876406.
- 78) I.A. Wahab, and L.H. Ismail, "Contemporary house with vernacular elements effect on natural ventilation in tropical climate," *International Journal For Research in Emerging Science and Technology E-ISSN 2349-7610*, 1 (5) (2014).
- 79) S. Thravalou, A. Michael, M. Neophytou, and M. Philokyprou, "The Ventilation Capacity of Earthen Vernacular Buildings with Timber Projections (Sachnisi) in Dense Urban Canyons - Findings from a Field Study in the Mediterranean," in: *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci*, 2023. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1196/1/012089.
- 80) M. Kamata, M. Imano, Y. Akamine, Y. Zheng, H. Hoshino, and Y.-F. Tu, "Analysis of Natural Cross-Ventilation for Building Environmental Control," in: 2010. doi:10.1007/978-4-431-99720-7_4.
- 81) K. Lavtižar, "Fundamentals of natural ventilation in buildings," *Igra Ustvarjalnosti - Creativy Game*, 2020 (08) (2020). doi:10.15292/iu-cg.2020.08.020-027.
- 82) J. Baas, M. Schotten, A. Plume, G. Côté, and R. Karimi, "Scopus as a curated, high-quality bibliometric data source for academic research in quantitative science studies," *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1 (1) (2020). doi:10.1162/qss_a_00019.
- 83) A. Yaman, A. Yoganingrum, Y. Yaniasih, and S. Riyanto, "TINJAUAN pustaka sistematis pada basis data pustaka digital: tren riset, metodologi, dan coverage fields," *BACA: JURNAL DOKUMENTASI DAN INFORMASI*, 40 (1) (2019). doi:10.14203/j.baca.v40i1.481.
- 84) N. Bin Ali, and B. Tanveer, "A comparison of citation sources for reference and citation-based search in systematic literature reviews," *E-Informatica Software Engineering Journal*, 16 (1) (2022). doi:10.37190/e-Inf220106.
- 85) A. Cortegiani, A. Manca, M. Lalu, and D. Moher, "Inclusion of predatory journals in scopus is inflating scholars' metrics and advancing careers," *Int J Public Health*, 65 (1) (2020). doi:10.1007/s00038-019-01318-w.
- 86) G.A. Saenz Tovar, and R. Alejandro Reta, "Vosviewer as a complementary tool to analyze the state of the art applied to electricity markets," in: 2022. doi:10.1109/argencon55245.2022.9940131.
- 87) I. Shkola, M. Andriichuk, and A. Petruniok, "Using vosviewer to analyze articles, indexing in pubmed database, about emerging infections," *Ukrainian Scientific Medical Youth Journal*, 134 (4) (2022). doi:10.32345/usmyj.4(134).2022.53-61.
- 88) R. Song, Y. Li, B. Ye, G. Li, and L. Zou, "The research status and hotspots of photoelectrochemical aptasensor: a bibliometric review based on vos viewer," *J Electrochem Soc*, 170 (6) (2023). doi:10.1149/1945-7111/ace008.
- 89) N. Jan van Eck, and L. Waltman, "VOSviewer Manual," n.d.
- 90) E. Orduña-Malea, and R. Costas, "Link-based approach to study scientific software usage: the case of vosviewer," *Scientometrics*, 126 (9) (2021). doi:10.1007/s11192-021-04082-y.
- 91) V. Gautam, and S. Gupta, "Envisaging modularity detecting communities in networks: gephi visuals," *Evergreen*, 10 (4) (2023). doi:10.5109/7160929.
- 92) A.Y. Shestakova, D.O. Korolev, A.A. Afanasyev, I. V. Nikiforov, and O.A. Yusupova, "Scopus publications database analysis using its API," in: 2023. doi:10.1117/12.2669237.
- 93) J. Morales, L. Munoz, and A. Fong, "Proposal for the evaluation of the quality of the Metadata for a Research Data Repository," in: *Proceedings - 2022 8th International Engineering, Sciences and Technology Conference, IESTEC 2022*, 2022. doi:10.1109/IESTEC54539.2022.00043.
- 94) P. Fornacciari, M. Mordonini, M. Nonelli, L. Sani, and M. Tomaiuolo, "Knowledge discovery on scopus," in: *CEUR Workshop Proc*, 2017.
- 95) F. Boyle, and D. Sherman, "Scopus???: the product and its development," *Serials Librarian*, 49 (3) (2005). doi:10.1300/J123v49n03_12.
- 96) R. De Jong, and D. Bus, "VOSviewer: putting research into context," *Research Software Community Leiden*, (2023). doi:10.21428/a1847950.acdc99d6.
- 97) M. Rofik, A. Anekawati, and I. Isyanto, "PELATIHAN mapping research with vos viewer depending on publish or peris," *Community Development Journal: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 3 (3) (2022). doi:10.31004/cdj.v3i3.8473.
- 98) C. Chen, J. Zhang, and M.S. Vogeley, "Making sense of the evolution of a scientific domain: a visual analytic study of the sloan digital sky survey research," *Scientometrics*, 83 (3) (2010). doi:10.1007/s11192-009-0123-x.
- 99) A. Darko, and A.P.-C. Chan, "Applying science mapping in built environment research," in: *Secondary Research Methods in the Built Environment*, 2021. doi:10.1201/9781003000532-9.
- 100) S. Xu, L. Hao, X. An, H. Pang, and T. Li, "Review

- on emerging research topics with key-route main path analysis,” *Scientometrics*, 122 (1) (2020). doi:10.1007/s11192-019-03288-5.
- 101) J. Xie, G. Zhang, Y. Li, X. Yan, L. Zang, Q. Liu, D. Chen, M. Sui, and Y. He, “A bibliometric analysis of forest gap research during 1980–2021,” *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15 (3) (2023). doi:10.3390/su15031994.
- 102) F.S. Arsad, R. Hod, N. Ahmad, M. Baharom, and M.H. Ja’afar, “Assessment of indoor thermal comfort temperature and related behavioural adaptations: a systematic review,” *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30 (29) (2023). doi:10.1007/s11356-023-27089-9.
- 103) A.A. Olsen, “Indoor Climate,” in: *Applying Physical Ergonomics to Modern Ship Design*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024: pp. 385–394. doi:10.1007/978-3-031-57974-5_34.
- 104) S.N. Rosminahar, M.N.H. Mat, and E.M. Yusup, “Mesh refinement for dynamics airflow in health care,” *International Journal of Integrated Engineering*, 16 (6) 90–99 (2024). doi:10.30880/ijie.2024.16.06.009.
- 105) S. Marashian, A. Vadiée, O. Abouali, and S. Sadrizadeh, “Enhancing Indoor Environmental Simulations: A Comprehensive Review of CFD Methods,” in: *Proceedings of the 64th International Conference of Scandinavian Simulation Society, SIMS 2023 Västerås, Sweden, September 25-28, 2023*, 2023. doi:10.3384/ecp200046.
- 106) A.K.M. Yahia, Dr.Md.M. Rahman, M. Shahjalal, and A. Morshed, “SUSTAINABLE materials selection in building design and construction,” *International Journal of Science and Engineering*, 1 (4) 106–119 (2024). doi:10.62304/ijse.v1i04.199.
- 107) Peter.J. Irga, G. Mullen, R. Fleck, S. Matheson, Sara.J. Wilkinson, and Fraser.R. Torpy, “Volatile organic compounds emitted by humans indoors– a review on the measurement, test conditions, and analysis techniques,” *Build Environ*, 255 111442 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111442.
- 108) H. Guan, Q. Jia, Z. Guo, X. Han, H. Zhang, L. Hao, C. Wu, and J. Liu, “Emissions of semi-volatile organic compounds from architectural coatings and polyvinyl chloride floorings: microchamber method,” *Molecules*, 29 (18) 4445 (2024). doi:10.3390/molecules29184445.
- 109) M.-H. Yuan, S. Kang, and K.-S. Cho, “A review of phyto- and microbial-remediation of indoor volatile organic compounds,” *Chemosphere*, 359 142120 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2024.142120.
- 110) A.M. Khan, M.A. Tariq, S.K.U. Rehman, T. Saeed, F.K. Alqahtani, and M. Sherif, “BIM integration with xai using lime and moo for automated green building energy performance analysis,” *Energies (Basel)*, 17 (13) 3295 (2024). doi:10.3390/en17133295.
- 111) A. Singh, and Divyashree, “Enhancing Green Building Performance through Integrated BIM Model Optimization Strategies,” in: *Unnati Shiksha*, 2024. doi:10.62919/jggj1232.
- 112) U. Bharadwaj, and A. Singh, “Sustainable green construction practices using griha parameters and bim tools implementation on building design,” *Evergreen*, 11 (3) 1641–1654 (2024). doi:10.5109/7236818.
- 113) W.H. Wan Ismail, M.F. Mohamad, N. Ikegaya, J. Chung, C. Hirose, A. Abd Razak, and A. Mohd Azmi, “Comprehensive comparisons of rans, les, and experiments over cross-ventilated building under sheltered conditions,” *Build Environ*, 254 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111402.
- 114) K.S. Hu, and T.I.-P. Shih, “Large-eddy vs. reynolds-averaged navier–stokes simulations of flow and heat transfer in a u-duct with unsteady flow separation,” *Energies (Basel)*, 17 (10) 2414 (2024). doi:10.3390/en17102414.
- 115) G.S. Brager, and R.J. De Dear, “Thermal adaptation in the built environment: a literature review,” *Energy Build*, 27 (1) (1998). doi:10.1016/s0378-7788(97)00053-4.
- 116) S. Vardoulakis, B.E.A. Fisher, K. Pericleous, and N. Gonzalez-Flesca, “Modelling air quality in street canyons: a review,” *Atmos Environ*, 37 (2) (2003). doi:10.1016/S1352-2310(02)00857-9.
- 117) I. Zabalza Bribián, A. Valero Capilla, and A. Aranda Usón, “Life cycle assessment of building materials: comparative analysis of energy and environmental impacts and evaluation of the eco-efficiency improvement potential,” *Build Environ*, 46 (5) (2011). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2010.12.002.
- 118) Q. Chen, “Ventilation performance prediction for buildings: a method overview and recent applications,” *Build Environ*, 44 (4) (2009). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.05.025.
- 119) C.J. Weschler, and W.W. Nazaroff, “Semivolatile organic compounds in indoor environments,” *Atmos Environ*, 42 (40) (2008). doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2008.09.052.
- 120) B. Blocken, “50 years of computational wind engineering: past, present and future,” *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 129 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.jweia.2014.03.008.
- 121) R. Ramponi, and B. Blocken, “CFD simulation of cross-ventilation for a generic isolated building: impact of computational parameters,” *Build Environ*, 53 (2012). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2012.01.004.
- 122) Y. Lu, Z. Wu, R. Chang, and Y. Li, “Building information modeling (bim) for green buildings: a critical review and future directions,” *Autom Constr*, 83 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.autcon.2017.08.024.

- 123) B. Blocken, "LES over runs in building simulation for outdoor and indoor applications: a foregone conclusion?," *Build Simul*, 11 (5) (2018). doi:10.1007/s12273-018-0459-3.
- 124) B. Chenari, J. Dias Carrilho, and M. Gameiro da Silva, "Towards sustainable, energy-efficient and healthy ventilation strategies in buildings: a review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 59 1426–1447 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.01.074.
- 125) T. Hussein, T. Glytsos, J. Ondráček, P. Dohányosová, V. Ždímal, K. Hämeri, M. Lazaridis, J. Smolík, and M. Kulmala, "Particle size characterization and emission rates during indoor activities in a house," *Atmos Environ*, 40 (23) 4285–4307 (2006). doi:10.1016/j.atmosenv.2006.03.053.
- 126) G.A. Florides, S.A. Tassou, S.A. Kalogirou, and L.C. Wrobel, "Measures used to lower building energy consumption and their cost effectiveness," *Appl Energy*, 73 (3–4) 299–328 (2002). doi:10.1016/S0306-2619(02)00119-8.
- 127) M. Hamdy, A. Hasan, and K. Siren, "Applying a multi-objective optimization approach for design of low-emission cost-effective dwellings," *Build Environ*, 46 (1) 109–123 (2011). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2010.07.006.
- 128) S. Vardoulakis, E. Giagloglou, S. Steinle, A. Davis, A. Sleuwenhoek, K.S. Galea, K. Dixon, and J.O. Crawford, "Indoor exposure to selected air pollutants in the home environment: a systematic review," *Int J Environ Res Public Health*, 17 (23) 1–24 (2020). doi:10.3390/ijerph17238972.
- 129) T. Kubota, D.T.H. Chyee, and S. Ahmad, "The effects of night ventilation technique on indoor thermal environment for residential buildings in hot-humid climate of malaysia," *Energy Build*, 41 (8) 829–839 (2009). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2009.03.008.
- 130) J. Hirunlabh, W. Kongduang, P. Namprakai, and J. Khedari, "Study of natural ventilation of houses by a metallic solar wall under tropical climate," *Renew Energy*, 18 (1) 109–119 (1999). doi:10.1016/S0960-1481(98)00783-6.
- 131) W. Ye, X. Zhang, J. Gao, G. Cao, X. Zhou, and X. Su, "Indoor air pollutants, ventilation rate determinants and potential control strategies in chinese dwellings: a literature review," *Science of the Total Environment*, 586 696–729 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.02.047.
- 132) N.P. Gao, J.L. Niu, M. Perino, and P. Heiselberg, "The airborne transmission of infection between flats in high-rise residential buildings: tracer gas simulation," *Build Environ*, 43 (11) (2008). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2007.10.023.
- 133) J. Khedari, B. Boonsri, and J. Hirunlabh, "Ventilation impact of a solar chimney on indoor temperature fluctuation and air change in a school building," *Energy Build*, 32 (1) 89–93 (2000). doi:10.1016/S0378-7788(99)00042-0.
- 134) N.M. Mateus, A. Pinto, and G.C. Da Graça, "Validation of energyplus thermal simulation of a double skin naturally and mechanically ventilated test cell," *Energy Build*, 75 511–522 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2014.02.043.
- 135) R. Stasi, F. Ruggiero, and U. Berardi, "Influence of cross-ventilation cooling potential on thermal comfort in high-rise buildings in a hot and humid climate," *Build Environ*, 248 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.111096.
- 136) A. Budianto, R. Wirawan, R.R. Illahi, D.W. Kurniawidi, S. Rahayu, A.A. Ngurah Nara Kusuma, and A.T. Alaydrus, "A gravimetry-based fine particle concentration measurement system for humid environment using graphene oxide layer," *Evergreen*, 10 (3) (2023). doi:10.5109/7151690.
- 137) W. Su, Z. Ai, J. Liu, B. Yang, and F. Wang, "Maintaining an acceptable indoor air quality of spaces by intentional natural ventilation or intermittent mechanical ventilation with minimum energy use," *Appl Energy*, 348 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121504.
- 138) D. Sharma, V.K. Modi, and C. Kumar, "Techno-economic analysis of insulating bricks used in educational building made by local available agricultural waste," *Evergreen*, 10 (4) (2023). doi:10.5109/7160914.
- 139) Chairunnisa, Muhammad Penta Helios, A. Andini, Agus Prasetyo Nuryadi, A. Maswan, H. Sutriyanto, H. Pujowidodo, Bambang Teguh Prasetyo, Ariyana Dwiputra Nugraha, and N. Cahyo, "Numerical modelling co-firing combustion in the existing coal-fired power plant: case study in paiton 9 power plant," *Evergreen*, 11 (3) 2638–2649 (2024). doi:10.5109/7236903.
- 140) L.A. Rasheed, J.A.K. Mohammed, and R.A. Jessam, "Performance enhancement of solar air heater by integrating innovative absorber design and automatic control flow rate," *Evergreen*, 10 (3) (2023). doi:10.5109/7151693.
- 141) A. Sarkar, R. Govindaraj, J. Jyotsna Rao, and U. Pal, "Effect of Open and Closed State of Windows on the Indoor Air Quality of Residential Housing," in: *INDICON 2022 - 2022 IEEE 19th India Council International Conference*, 2022. doi:10.1109/INDICON56171.2022.10039794.
- 142) V. V Balakin, "Air quality upgrading in residential areas using architectural methods," *IOP Conf Ser Mater Sci Eng*, 1079 (5) (2021). doi:10.1088/1757-899x/1079/5/052039.
- 143) M.F. Mohamed, S.N. Raman, T.M.I. Pratama, and W.F.M. Yusoff, "Outdoor Environment of Low-cost Housing: A case study of Flat Taman Desa Sentosa,"

- in: E3S Web of Conferences, 2014. doi:10.1051/e3sconf/20140301005.
- 144) E. Stachura, "A study in polish housing conditions. methodology and building typology characteristics," *Remav*, 21 (1) (2013). doi:10.2478/remav-2013-0004.
- 145) I. Kang, A. McCreery, P. Azimi, A. Gramigna, G. Baca, W. Hayes, T. Crowder, R. Scheu, A. Evens, and B. Stephens, "Impacts of residential indoor air quality and environmental risk factors on adult asthma-related health outcomes in chicago, il," *J Expo Sci Environ Epidemiol*, 33 (3) (2023). doi:10.1038/s41370-022-00503-z.
- 146) R.S. Tobin, M. Bourgeau, R. Otson, and G.C. Wood, "Residential indoor air quality guidelines," *Indoor and Built Environment*, 2 (5-6) (1993). doi:10.1177/1420326X9300200503.
- 147) A. Aflaki, N. Mahyuddin, Z. Al-Cheikh Mahmoud, and M.R. Baharum, "A review on natural ventilation applications through building façade components and ventilation openings in tropical climates," *Energy Build*, 101 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.04.033.
- 148) F. Jomehzadeh, P. Nejat, J.K. Calautit, M.B.M. Yusof, S.A. Zaki, B.R. Hughes, and M.N.A.W.M. Yazid, "A review on windcatcher for passive cooling and natural ventilation in buildings, part 1: indoor air quality and thermal comfort assessment," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 70 (2017). doi:10.1016/j.rser.2016.11.254.
- 149) M.K. Singh, S. Mahapatra, and S.K. Atreya, "Bioclimatism and vernacular architecture of north-east india," *Build Environ*, 44 (5) (2009). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.06.008.
- 150) H. Montazeri, and F. Montazeri, "CFD simulation of cross-ventilation in buildings using rooftop wind-catchers: impact of outlet openings," *Renew Energy*, 118 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.renene.2017.11.032.
- 151) R. Yao, V. Costanzo, X. Li, Q. Zhang, and B. Li, "The effect of passive measures on thermal comfort and energy conservation. a case study of the hot summer and cold winter climate in the yangtze river region," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 15 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.job.2017.11.012.
- 152) H. Montazeri, and R. Azizian, "Experimental study on natural ventilation performance of one-sided wind catcher," *Build Environ*, 43 (12) (2008). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2008.01.005.
- 153) C. Heracleous, and A. Michael, "Experimental assessment of the impact of natural ventilation on indoor air quality and thermal comfort conditions of educational buildings in the eastern mediterranean region during the heating period," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 26 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.job.2019.100917.
- 154) S. Attia, and S. Carlucci, "Impact of different thermal comfort models on zero energy residential buildings in hot climate," *Energy Build*, 102 (2015). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2015.05.017.
- 155) A.F. Tzikopoulos, M.C. Karatza, and J.A. Paravantis, "Modeling energy efficiency of bioclimatic buildings," *Energy Build*, 37 (5) (2005). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2004.09.002.
- 156) S. Kumar, J. Mathur, S. Mathur, M.K. Singh, and V. Loftness, "An adaptive approach to define thermal comfort zones on psychrometric chart for naturally ventilated buildings in composite climate of india," *Build Environ*, 109 (2016). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2016.09.023.
- 157) S. Heidari, A.H. Poshtiri, and Z.M. Gilvaei, "Enhancing thermal comfort and natural ventilation in residential buildings: a design and assessment of an integrated system with horizontal windcatcher and evaporative cooling channels," *Energy*, 289 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.energy.2023.130040.
- 158) M. Liu, S. Almazmumi, P. Cao, C. Jimenez-bescos, and J.K. Calautit, "Can windcatcher's natural ventilation beat the chill? a view from heat loss and thermal discomfort," *Build Environ*, 247 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2023.110916.
- 159) M. Alnsour, Zakaria Al-Omari, T. Rawashdeh, and Ayat oudat, "Shaping tomorrow's community requires right decisions to be made today through investment in sustainable infrastructure: an international review," *Evergreen*, 11 (3) 1508-1529 (2024). doi:10.5109/7236808.
- 160) S.K. Gupta, P.R. Chanda, and A. Biswas, "A 2e, energy and environment performance of an optimized vernacular house for passive cooling - case of north-east india," *Build Environ*, 229 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.109909.
- 161) F. Yulia, N. Pajri, Nasruddin, Byan Wahyu Riyandwita, Yose Fachmi Buys, S. Hastuty, Arie Sukma Jaya, Nonni Soraya Sambudi, and Sylvia Ayu Pradanawati, "Predicting cooling load and energy consumption of coconut oil as phase change material for thermal management in a residential building using artificial neural network," *Evergreen*, 11 (3) 2761-2773 (2024). doi:10.5109/7236915.
- 162) W. Zhong, T. Zhang, and T. Tamura, "CFD simulation of convective heat transfer on vernacular sustainable architecture: validation and application of methodology," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11 (15) (2019). doi:10.3390/su11154231.
- 163) Firas Basim Ismail, Hussein A Kazem, Muhammad Ammar Bin Suhailie, and Miqdam T. Chaichan, "Climate change mitigation through innovative solar-powered car ventilation system design and evaluation for the malaysian context," *Evergreen*, 11 (3) 1856-

- 1869 (2024). doi:10.5109/7236837.
- 164) L. Dipasquale, J. Ammendola, L. Montoni, E.P. Ferrari, and M. Zambelli, "Harnessing vernacular knowledge for contemporary sustainable design through a collaborative digital platform," *Heritage*, 7 (9) 5251–5267 (2024). doi:10.3390/heritage7090247.
- 165) S. Wijaksono, "Passive designs of low-income housing with natural ventilation in tropical region," *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci*, 1324 (1) 012051 (2024). doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1324/1/012051.
- 166) W. Zhong, Y. Pan, W. Xiao, and T. Zhang, "Identifying bioclimatic techniques for sustainable low-rise high-density residential units: comparative analysis on the ventilation performance of vernacular dwellings in china," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 80 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.jobe.2023.108008.
- 167) F. López Plazas, and C. Sáenz de Tejada, "Natural ventilation to improve indoor air quality (iaq) in existing homes: the development of health-based and context-specific user guidelines," *Energy Build*, 314 114248 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114248.
- 168) J.A. Qadourah, "Improving natural ventilation multi-story buildings within hot and dry climates: a cfd study of windcatcher performance," *Civil Engineering and Architecture*, 12 (2) (2024). doi:10.13189/cea.2024.120225.
- 169) A. Bekleyen, and Y. Melikoğlu, "An investigation on the thermal effects of windcatchers," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 34 (2021). doi:10.1016/j.jobe.2020.101942.
- 170) H. Nazir, S. Abro, and A. Iqbal, "Windcatchers as a green ventilation device: a lost tale from hyderabad, sindh, pakistan," *J Asian Afr Stud*, (2024). doi:10.1177/00219096241230486.
- 171) R. Baydoun, and A.R. Sopian, "EVALUATING the effect of mashrabiya and perforated malay carving window on the indoor natural ventilation performance of living space," *Journal of Architecture, Planning and Construction Management*, 12 (2) (2022). doi:10.31436/japcm.v12i2.694.
- 172) D. Taşkan, and A.B. Ismaeel, "An architectural element: mashrabiya," *Art-Sanat Dergisi*, (17) (2022). doi:10.26650/ARTSANAT.2022.17.841296.
- 173) kking88gb, "Mitsu-kude test fit," *OpenAIRE*, (2021). doi:https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10334901.
- 174) A. Mukhtar, M.Z. Yusoff, and K.C. Ng, "The potential influence of building optimization and passive design strategies on natural ventilation systems in underground buildings: the state of the art," *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 92 (2019). doi:10.1016/j.tust.2019.103065.
- 175) F. Jomehzadeh, H.M. Hussen, J.K. Calautit, P. Nejat, and M.S. Ferwati, "Natural ventilation by windcatcher (badgir): a review on the impacts of geometry, microclimate and macroclimate," *Energy Build*, 226 (2020). doi:10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110396.
- 176) A. Ghaffarianhoseini, U. Berardi, N.D. Dahlan, and A. Ghaffarianhoseini, "What can we learn from malay vernacular houses?," *Sustain Cities Soc*, 13 (2014). doi:10.1016/j.scs.2014.04.008.
- 177) M.M. Elwan, "The role of traditional lattice window 'mashrabiya' in delivering single-sided ventilation-a cfd study," *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology*, 68 (9) (2020). doi:10.14445/22315381/IJETT-V68I9P221.
- 178) H.M. Mazraeh, and M. Pazhouhanfar, "Functionalism of wind renewable energy in vernacular elements of wind catcher and moshabak (case study: qeshm island)," *Journal of Urban and Environmental Engineering*, 14 (1) (2020). doi:10.4090/juee.2020.v14n1.161172.
- 179) H. Sun, H. Zhong, A. Dik, K. Ding, C. Jimenez-Bescos, and J.K. Calautit, "Numerical investigation of evaporative cooling strategies on the aero-thermal performance of courtyard buildings in hot-dry climates," *Build Environ*, 258 111588 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2024.111588.
- 180) H. Ramezani, and E. Reza, "The consequence of combining indigenous techniques with a flexible design to reduce energy consumption in residential buildings for future architecture," *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14 (21) (2022). doi:10.3390/su142113958.
- 181) A. Zaki, P. Richards, and R. Sharma, "The effect of onset turbulent flows on ventilation with a two-sided rooftop windcatcher," *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 225 (2022). doi:10.1016/j.jweia.2022.104993.
- 182) L.G. Carreto-Hernandez, S.L. Moya, W.G. Báez-García, L.C. Sandoval Herazo, A. Francisco-Hernandez, J.C. Hernández-Jerónimo, and E. Téllez-Velázquez, "Numerical-experimental investigation of a wind tower-room sustainable system: a parametric analysis of the mixed convection with humidification," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 91 109624 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.jobe.2024.109624.
- 183) M. Liu, C. Jimenez-Bescos, and J. Calautit, "CFD investigation of a natural ventilation wind tower system with solid tube banks heat recovery for mild-cold climate," *Journal of Building Engineering*, 45 (2022). doi:10.1016/j.jobe.2021.103570.
- 184) S. Schelbach, "Applying traditional passive concepts of resource efficiency and climate adaptation to improve the energy efficiency of modern buildings: A case study in Thessaloniki, Greece," in: *WIT Transactions on the Built Environment*, 2014. doi:10.2495/ARC140101.
- 185) X. Chen, H. Yang, and W. Zhang, "Simulation-based approach to optimize passively designed buildings: a

- case study on a typical architectural form in hot and humid climates,” *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 82 (2018). doi:10.1016/j.rser.2017.06.018.
- 186) A.N. Yussupov, and A.A. Yussupova, “Ecological houses of southern kazakhstan using renewable energy sources,” *Smart and Sustainable Built Environment*, 11 (3) (2022). doi:10.1108/SASBE-06-2020-0088.
- 187) M. Adam, and A.A. Aziz, “Retrospective for perspective towards passive low energy modern housing design,” in: 22nd International Conference, PLEA 2005: Passive and Low Energy Architecture - Environmental Sustainability: The Challenge of Awareness in Developing Societies, Proceedings, 2005.
- 188) “International conference on buildings and environment, envibuild 2013,” *Adv Mat Res*, 899 (2014).
- 189) J. Pike, “Construction methods which can achieve A3 rating at minimal extra cost,” in: PLEA 2008 - Towards Zero Energy Building: 25th PLEA International Conference on Passive and Low Energy Architecture, Conference Proceedings, 2008.
- 190) M. Thelwall, and S. Pinfield, “The accuracy of field classifications for journals in scopus,” *Scientometrics*, 129 (2) (2024). doi:10.1007/s11192-023-04901-4.
- 191) M. Thelwall, and S. Pinfield, “Are scopus journal field classifications ever misleading?,” Cornell University, (2023).
- 192) I. Febijanto, S. Steven, N. Nadirah, H. Bahua, A. Shoiful, Dian P. Dewanti, I P. Angga Kristyawan, Khalda A. Haris, M. Yuliani, M. Hanif, Muhammad H. Robbani, Naufal R. Yusuf, Prihartanto, P. Alfatri, Reba A. Pratama, W. Purwanta, Wiharja, R. Nugroho, and Satria K. Ramadhan, “Municipal solid waste (msw) reduction through incineration for electricity purposes and its environmental performance: a case study in bantargebang, west java, indonesia,” *Evergreen*, 11 (1) 32–45 (2024). doi:10.5109/7172186.
- 193) D. Singh, J. Dadhich, Y. Bhadoriya, and S. Taneja, “A review on the prospects of various gaseous fuel as an automotive fuel and for reducing environmental pollution,” *Evergreen*, 10 (4) (2023). doi:10.5109/7160925.
- 194) A.H. Chohan, J. Awad, Y. Elkahlout, and M. Abuarkub, “Evaluating windcatchers in uae heritage architecture: a pathway to zero-energy cooling solutions,” *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 15 (10) 102936 (2024). doi:10.1016/j.asej.2024.102936.
- 195) A. Martín-Martín, E. Orduna-Malea, and E. Delgado López-Cózar, “Coverage of highly-cited documents in google scholar, web of science, and scopus: a multidisciplinary comparison,” *Scientometrics*, 116 (3) (2018). doi:10.1007/s11192-018-2820-9.
- 196) M. Wijewickrema, “Reality or illusion: comparing google scholar and scopus data for predatory journals,” *Portal*, 24 (1) (2024). doi:10.1353/pla.2024.a916989.